

Single-Layer Bordered Even and Odd Orders Primes Magic Squares: Orders 120 and 121

Inder J. Taneja¹

The work is also available at author's site:

Even Orders: <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=19224>

Odd orders: <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=19258>

Abstract

*This work bring for the first time **concentric prime magic squares** of orders 121 and 121. Sometimes, these types of magic squares we call as **single-layer** or **single-digit bordered** magic squares. The work is concentrated specially to prime number entries. In case of even orders, we start with prime magic square of order 4. Increasing layer by layer we get the magic squares of orders 6, 8, 10, etc. In case of odd orders we start with prime magic square order 3. Increasing layer by layer we get magic squares of orders 5, 7, 9, etc. Initially this work is for the orders 120 and 121. In future we shall go on increasing this order. In case of even orders, we have two types of results. One is up to order 80. It is with lower magic sums. The second type is up to order 120. In this case magaic sums are bigger. This is shown by examples. In case of odd orders. the there is only type, i.e, from order 3 to 121.*

Keywords: magic squares, bordered magic squares, prime numbers, prime magic squares, embedded or nested or concentric magic squares, recreational mathematics.

¹Formerly, Professor of Mathematics, Federal University of Santa Catarina, Florianópolis, SC, Brazil (1978-2012).

Also worked at Delhi University, India (1976-1978).

E-mail: ijtaneja@gmail.com;

Web-sites: <http://inderjtaneja.com>; <http://numbers-magic.com>;

Twitter: @IJTANEJA; **Instagram:** @crazynumbers.

Contents

1 Introduction	4
2 Even Order Concentric Prime Magic Squares	4
2.1 Prime Magic Square of Order 4	4
2.2 Prime Magic Square of Order 6	5
2.3 Prime Magic Square of Order 8	5
2.4 Prime Magic Square of Order 10	6
2.5 Prime Magic Square of Order 12	6
2.6 Prime Magic Square of Order 14	7
2.7 Prime Magic Square of Order 16	8
2.8 Prime Magic Square of Order 18	9
2.9 Prime Magic Square of Order 20	10
2.10 Prime Magic Square of Order 22	11
2.11 Prime Magic Square of Order 24	12
2.12 Prime Magic Square of Order 26	13
2.13 Prime Magic Square of Order 28	14
2.14 Prime Magic Square of Order 30	15
2.15 Prime Magic Square of Order 32	16
2.16 Prime Magic Square of Order 34	17
2.17 Prime Magic Square of OrderS 36-120	17
3 Odd Order Concentric Prime Magic Squares	19
3.1 Prime Magic Square of Order 3	19
3.2 Prime Magic Square of Order 5	19
3.3 Prime Magic Square of Order 7	20
3.4 Prime Magic Square of Order 9	20
3.5 Prime Magic Square of Order 11	21
3.6 Prime Magic Square of Order 13	21

3.7 Prime Magic Square of Order 15	22
3.8 Prime Magic Square of Order 17	23
3.9 Prime Magic Square of Order 19	24
3.10 Prime Magic Square of Order 21	25
3.11 Prime Magic Square of Order 23	26
3.12 Prime Magic Square of Order 25	27
3.13 Prime Magic Square of Order 27	28
3.14 Prime Magic Square of Order 29	29
3.15 Prime Magic Square of Order 31	30
3.16 Prime Magic Square of Order 33	31
3.17 Prime Magic Square of OrderS 35-121	31
4 Author’s Contribution to Recreation of Numbers and Magic Squares	32

1 Introduction

This work brings **single-layer** or **single-digit bordered** or **concentric** magic squares of even and odd orders. By **single-layer** or **single-digit bordered** or **concentric** magic squares we understand that if we remove the **upper-layers** or **upper-borders** still we are left with magic squares of lower orders. Here, the work is for prime numbers entries. For sequential numbers, the readers can see the authors work [15, 16, 18]. It is done for both even and odd orders. For even orders the starting magic square is of order 4. For odd order the starting magic square is of order 3. Recently, the author [9, 10] also worked on **block-structured** procedure for prime number entries for the orders 6 to 23. Also refer [8] for the **block-structured** prime magic square of order 1220 with equal sum blocks of prime magic squares of order 4.

Below are few examples given in two separate sections. One on even orders and another on odd orders. Excel sheets complete work are also attached.

2 Even Order Concentric Prime Magic Squares

Below are few examples of even order single-layer prime magic squares starting with magic square of order 4.

2.1 Prime Magic Square of Order 4

4	mgc				2000000
	306191	65951	934049	693809	2000000
	878651	799619	200381	121349	2000000
	517901	808553	191447	482099	2000000
	297257	325877	674123	702743	2000000
	2000000	2000000	2000000	2000000	2000000

It is prime magic square of order 4. All the primes are distinct.

2.2 Prime Magic Square of Order 6

6	mgc							3000000
	881591	86783	124739	940271	457889	508727		3000000
	149057	306191	65951	934049	693809	850943		3000000
	194963	878651	799619	200381	121349	805037		3000000
	349709	517901	808553	191447	482099	650291		3000000
	933407	297257	325877	674123	702743	66593		3000000
	491273	913217	875261	59729	542111	118409		3000000
	3000000	3000000	3000000	3000000	3000000	3000000		3000000

It contains the prime magic square of order 4 given above. All the primes are distinct.

2.3 Prime Magic Square of Order 8

8	mgc								4000000
	35801	71129	156089	167543	620657	997649	957701	993431	4000000
	466073	881591	86783	124739	940271	457889	508727	533927	4000000
	29201	149057	306191	65951	934049	693809	850943	970799	4000000
	979373	194963	878651	799619	200381	121349	805037	20627	4000000
	790379	349709	517901	808553	191447	482099	650291	209621	4000000
	919067	933407	297257	325877	674123	702743	66593	80933	4000000
	773537	491273	913217	875261	59729	542111	118409	226463	4000000
	6569	928871	843911	832457	379343	2351	42299	964199	4000000
	4000000	4000000	4000000	4000000	4000000	4000000	4000000	4000000	4000000

It contains the prime magic squares of orders 4 and 6 given above. All the primes are distinct.

2.4 Prime Magic Square of Order 10

10	mgc										5000000
	124067	382763	251117	157841	421559	24419	982061	959723	783599	912851	5000000
	19841	35801	71129	156089	167543	620657	997649	957701	993431	980159	5000000
	157721	466073	881591	86783	124739	940271	457889	508727	533927	842279	5000000
	364433	29201	149057	306191	65951	934049	693809	850943	970799	635567	5000000
	447683	979373	194963	878651	799619	200381	121349	805037	20627	552317	5000000
	804191	790379	349709	517901	808553	191447	482099	650291	209621	195809	5000000
	997973	919067	933407	297257	325877	674123	702743	66593	80933	2027	5000000
	998381	773537	491273	913217	875261	59729	542111	118409	226463	1619	5000000
	998561	6569	928871	843911	832457	379343	2351	42299	964199	1439	5000000
	87149	617237	748883	842159	578441	975581	17939	40277	216401	875933	5000000
	5000000	5000000	5000000	5000000	5000000	5000000	5000000	5000000	5000000	5000000	5000000

It contains the prime magic squares of orders 4, 6 and 8 given above. All the primes are distinct.

2.5 Prime Magic Square of Order 12

12	mgc											6000000	
	109001	192617	318161	246473	173429	133877	460829	836117	948581	996323	975083	609509	6000000
	22643	124067	382763	251117	157841	421559	24419	982061	959723	783599	912851	977357	6000000
	70997	19841	35801	71129	156089	167543	620657	997649	957701	993431	980159	929003	6000000
	352511	157721	466073	881591	86783	124739	940271	457889	508727	533927	842279	647489	6000000
	120299	364433	29201	149057	306191	65951	934049	693809	850943	970799	635567	879701	6000000
	65921	447683	979373	194963	878651	799619	200381	121349	805037	20627	552317	934079	6000000
	989939	804191	790379	349709	517901	808553	191447	482099	650291	209621	195809	10061	6000000
	919823	997973	919067	933407	297257	325877	674123	702743	66593	80933	2027	80177	6000000
	963701	998381	773537	491273	913217	875261	59729	542111	118409	226463	1619	36299	6000000
	997793	998561	6569	928871	843911	832457	379343	2351	42299	964199	1439	2207	6000000
	996881	87149	617237	748883	842159	578441	975581	17939	40277	216401	875933	3119	6000000
	390491	807383	681839	753527	826571	866123	539171	163883	51419	3677	24917	890999	6000000
	6000000	6000000	6000000	6000000	6000000	6000000	6000000	6000000	6000000	6000000	6000000	6000000	6000000

It contains the prime magic squares of orders 4, 6, 8 and 10 given above. All the primes are distinct.

2.6 Prime Magic Square of Order 14

14	mgc														7000000
	799343	149867	64661	221603	23357	81233	145967	889937	901133	942749	774491	905453	976883	123323	7000000
	54269	109001	192617	318161	246473	173429	133877	460829	836117	948581	996323	975083	609509	945731	7000000
	352349	22643	124067	382763	251117	157841	421559	24419	982061	959723	783599	912851	977357	647651	7000000
	113489	70997	19841	35801	71129	156089	167543	620657	997649	957701	993431	980159	929003	886511	7000000
	266177	352511	157721	466073	881591	86783	124739	940271	457889	508727	533927	842279	647489	733823	7000000
	30539	120299	364433	29201	149057	306191	65951	934049	693809	850943	970799	635567	879701	969461	7000000
	2903	65921	447683	979373	194963	878651	799619	200381	121349	805037	20627	552317	934079	997097	7000000
	277757	989939	804191	790379	349709	517901	808553	191447	482099	650291	209621	195809	10061	722243	7000000
	982769	919823	997973	919067	933407	297257	325877	674123	702743	66593	80933	2027	80177	17231	7000000
	812627	963701	998381	773537	491273	913217	875261	59729	542111	118409	226463	1619	36299	187373	7000000
	782501	997793	998561	6569	928871	843911	832457	379343	2351	42299	964199	1439	2207	217499	7000000
	705821	996881	87149	617237	748883	842159	578441	975581	17939	40277	216401	875933	3119	294179	7000000
	942779	390491	807383	681839	753527	826571	866123	539171	163883	51419	3677	24917	890999	57221	7000000
	876677	850133	935339	778397	976643	918767	854033	110063	98867	57251	225509	94547	23117	200657	7000000
	7000000	7000000	7000000	7000000	7000000	7000000	7000000	7000000	7000000	7000000	7000000	7000000	7000000	7000000	7000000

It contains the prime magic squares of orders 4, 6, 8, 10 and 12 given above. All the primes are distinct.

2.7 Prime Magic Square of Order 16

16	mgc																8000000
	415697	422453	281993	198659	164987	154613	430427	147377	460337	357989	915623	969863	990323	915869	997589	176201	8000000
	212183	799343	149867	64661	221603	23357	81233	145967	889937	901133	942749	774491	905453	976883	123323	787817	8000000
	423209	54269	109001	192617	318161	246473	173429	133877	460829	836117	948581	996323	975083	609509	945731	576791	8000000
	274019	352349	22643	124067	382763	251117	157841	421559	24419	982061	959723	783599	912851	977357	647651	725981	8000000
	238991	113489	70997	19841	35801	71129	156089	167543	620657	997649	957701	993431	980159	929003	886511	761009	8000000
	14723	266177	352511	157721	466073	881591	86783	124739	940271	457889	508727	533927	842279	647489	733823	985277	8000000
	163847	30539	120299	364433	29201	149057	306191	65951	934049	693809	850943	970799	635567	879701	969461	836153	8000000
	41513	2903	65921	447683	979373	194963	878651	799619	200381	121349	805037	20627	552317	934079	997097	958487	8000000
	12413	277757	989939	804191	790379	349709	517901	808553	191447	482099	650291	209621	195809	10061	722243	987587	8000000
	876077	982769	919823	997973	919067	933407	297257	325877	674123	702743	66593	80933	2027	80177	17231	123923	8000000
	933209	812627	963701	998381	773537	491273	913217	875261	59729	542111	118409	226463	1619	36299	187373	66791	8000000
	572927	782501	997793	998561	6569	928871	843911	832457	379343	2351	42299	964199	1439	2207	217499	427073	8000000
	998633	705821	996881	87149	617237	748883	842159	578441	975581	17939	40277	216401	875933	3119	294179	1367	8000000
	999239	942779	390491	807383	681839	753527	826571	866123	539171	163883	51419	3677	24917	890999	57221	761	8000000
	999521	876677	850133	935339	778397	976643	918767	854033	110063	98867	57251	225509	94547	23117	200657	479	8000000
	823799	577547	718007	801341	835013	845387	569573	852623	539663	642011	84377	30137	9677	84131	2411	584303	8000000
	8000000	8000000	8000000	8000000	8000000	8000000	8000000	8000000	8000000	8000000	8000000	8000000	8000000	8000000	8000000	8000000	8000000

It contains the prime magic squares of orders 4, 6, 8, 10, 12 and 14 given above. All the primes are distinct.

2.8 Prime Magic Square of Order 18

18	mgc																	9000000	
	199103	368939	382463	319811	87911	480587	467261	308051	423257	405047	472247	79601	849917	955313	979061	979211	999773	242447	9000000
	247799	415697	422453	281993	198659	164987	154613	430427	147377	460337	357989	915623	969863	990323	915869	997589	176201	752201	9000000
	255083	212183	799343	149867	64661	221603	23357	81233	145967	889937	901133	942749	774491	905453	976883	123323	787817	744917	9000000
	341057	423209	54269	109001	192617	318161	246473	173429	133877	460829	836117	948581	996323	975083	609509	945731	576791	658943	9000000
	362291	274019	352349	22643	124067	382763	251117	157841	421559	24419	982061	959723	783599	912851	977357	647651	725981	637709	9000000
	354479	238991	113489	70997	19841	35801	71129	156089	167543	620657	997649	957701	993431	980159	929003	886511	761009	645521	9000000
	299567	14723	266177	352511	157721	466073	881591	86783	124739	940271	457889	508727	533927	842279	647489	733823	985277	700433	9000000
	31091	163847	30539	120299	364433	29201	149057	306191	65951	934049	693809	850943	970799	635567	879701	969461	836153	968909	9000000
	89381	41513	2903	65921	447683	979373	194963	878651	799619	200381	121349	805037	20627	552317	934079	997097	958487	910619	9000000
	282011	12413	277757	989939	804191	790379	349709	517901	808553	191447	482099	650291	209621	195809	10061	722243	987587	717989	9000000
	441527	876077	982769	919823	997973	919067	933407	297257	325877	674123	702743	66593	80933	2027	80177	17231	123923	558473	9000000
	867467	933209	812627	963701	998381	773537	491273	913217	875261	59729	542111	118409	226463	1619	36299	187373	66791	132533	9000000
	926567	572927	782501	997793	998561	6569	928871	843911	832457	379343	2351	42299	964199	1439	2207	217499	427073	73433	9000000
	556709	998633	705821	996881	87149	617237	748883	842159	578441	975581	17939	40277	216401	875933	3119	294179	1367	443291	9000000
	997121	999239	942779	390491	807383	681839	753527	826571	866123	539171	163883	51419	3677	24917	890999	57221	761	2879	9000000
	998681	999521	876677	850133	935339	778397	976643	918767	854033	110063	98867	57251	225509	94547	23117	200657	479	1319	9000000
	992513	823799	577547	718007	801341	835013	845387	569573	852623	539663	642011	84377	30137	9677	84131	2411	584303	7487	9000000
	757553	631061	617537	680189	912089	519413	532739	691949	576743	594953	527753	920399	150083	44687	20939	20789	227	800897	9000000
	9000000	9000000	9000000	9000000	9000000	9000000	9000000	9000000	9000000	9000000	9000000	9000000	9000000	9000000	9000000	9000000	9000000	9000000	9000000

It contains the prime magic squares of orders 4, 6, 8, 10, 12, 14 and 16 given above. All the primes are distinct.

2.9 Prime Magic Square of Order 20

20	mgc																			10000000	
	550757	119447	355799	73331	304631	376709	44519	69911	181439	250751	292427	967763	348353	971561	997961	852239	978821	996461	969929	297191	10000000
	211811	199103	368939	382463	319811	87911	480587	467261	308051	423257	405047	472247	79601	849917	955313	979061	979211	999773	242447	788189	10000000
	253823	247799	415697	422453	281993	198659	164987	154613	430427	147377	460337	357989	915623	969863	990323	915869	997589	176201	752201	746177	10000000
	275921	255083	212183	799343	149867	64661	221603	23357	81233	145967	889937	901133	942749	774491	905453	976883	123323	787817	744917	724079	10000000
	58229	341057	423209	54269	109001	192617	318161	246473	173429	133877	460829	836117	948581	996323	975083	609509	945731	576791	658943	941771	10000000
	330689	362291	274019	352349	22643	124067	382763	251117	157841	421559	24419	982061	959723	783599	912851	977357	647651	725981	637709	669311	10000000
	172259	354479	238991	113489	70997	19841	35801	71129	156089	167543	620657	997649	957701	993431	980159	929003	886511	761009	645521	827741	10000000
	151703	299567	14723	266177	352511	157721	466073	881591	86783	124739	940271	457889	508727	533927	842279	647489	733823	985277	700433	848297	10000000
	304553	31091	163847	30539	120299	364433	29201	149057	306191	65951	934049	693809	850943	970799	635567	879701	969461	836153	968909	695447	10000000
	341597	89381	41513	2903	65921	447683	979373	194963	878651	799619	200381	121349	805037	20627	552317	934079	997097	958487	910619	658403	10000000
	400523	282011	12413	277757	989939	804191	790379	349709	517901	808553	191447	482099	650291	209621	195809	10061	722243	987587	717989	599477	10000000
	125201	441527	876077	982769	919823	997973	919067	933407	297257	325877	674123	702743	66593	80933	2027	80177	17231	123923	558473	874799	10000000
	912083	867467	933209	812627	963701	998381	773537	491273	913217	875261	59729	542111	118409	226463	1619	36299	187373	66791	132533	87917	10000000
	229127	926567	572927	782501	997793	998561	6569	928871	843911	832457	379343	2351	42299	964199	1439	2207	217499	427073	73433	770873	10000000
	984119	556709	998633	705821	996881	87149	617237	748883	842159	578441	975581	17939	40277	216401	875933	3119	294179	1367	443291	15881	10000000
	995747	997121	999239	942779	390491	807383	681839	753527	826571	866123	539171	163883	51419	3677	24917	890999	57221	761	2879	4253	10000000
	999491	998681	999521	876677	850133	935339	778397	976643	918767	854033	110063	98867	57251	225509	94547	23117	200657	479	1319	509	10000000
	999749	992513	823799	577547	718007	801341	835013	845387	569573	852623	539663	642011	84377	30137	9677	84131	2411	584303	7487	251	10000000
	999809	757553	631061	617537	680189	912089	519413	532739	691949	576743	594953	527753	920399	150083	44687	20939	20789	227	800897	191	10000000
	702809	880553	644201	926669	695369	623291	955481	930089	818561	749249	707573	32237	651647	28439	2039	147761	21179	3539	30071	449243	10000000
	10000000	10000000	10000000	10000000	10000000	10000000	10000000	10000000	10000000	10000000	10000000	10000000	10000000	10000000	10000000	10000000	10000000	10000000	10000000	10000000	10000000

It contains the prime magic squares of orders 4, 6, 8, 10, 12, 14, 16 and 18 given above. All the primes are distinct.

2.10 Prime Magic Square of Order 22

22	mgc																				11000000	
289127	161753	239699	15671	287867	499679	412289	266153	66161	438953	126683	123203	126359	686339	967229	979949	826349	973151	989909	999431	999029	525017	11000000
496841	550757	119447	355799	73331	304631	376709	44519	69911	181439	250751	292427	967763	348353	971561	997961	852239	978821	996461	969929	297191	503159	11000000
77783	211811	199103	368939	382463	319811	87911	480587	467261	308051	423257	405047	472247	79601	849917	955313	979061	979211	999773	242447	788189	922217	11000000
335417	253823	247799	415697	422453	281993	198659	164987	154613	430427	147377	460337	357989	915623	969863	990323	915869	997589	176201	752201	746177	664583	11000000
21383	275921	255083	212183	799343	149867	64661	221603	23357	81233	145967	889937	901133	942749	774491	905453	976883	123323	787817	744917	724079	978617	11000000
302873	58229	341057	423209	54269	109001	192617	318161	246473	173429	133877	460829	836117	948581	996323	975083	609509	945731	576791	658943	941771	697127	11000000
149519	330689	362291	274019	352349	22643	124067	382763	251117	157841	421559	24419	982061	959723	783599	912851	977357	647651	725981	637709	669311	850481	11000000
182681	172259	354479	238991	113489	70997	19841	35801	71129	156089	167543	620657	997649	957701	993431	980159	929003	886511	761009	645521	827741	817319	11000000
428411	151703	299567	14723	266177	352511	157721	466073	881591	86783	124739	940271	457889	508727	533927	842279	647489	733823	985277	700433	848297	571589	11000000
109541	304553	31091	163847	30539	120299	364433	29201	149057	306191	65951	934049	693809	850943	970799	635567	879701	969461	836153	968909	695447	890459	11000000
48869	341597	89381	41513	2903	65921	447683	979373	194963	878651	799619	200381	121349	805037	20627	552317	934079	997097	958487	910619	658403	951131	11000000
91529	400523	282011	12413	277757	989939	804191	790379	349709	517901	808553	191447	482099	650291	209621	195809	10061	722243	987587	717989	599477	908471	11000000
222269	125201	441527	876077	982769	919823	997973	919067	933407	297257	325877	674123	702743	66593	80933	2027	80177	17231	123923	558473	874799	777731	11000000
993401	912083	867467	933209	812627	963701	998381	773537	491273	913217	875261	59729	542111	118409	226463	1619	36299	187373	66791	132533	87917	6599	11000000
829877	229127	926567	572927	782501	997793	998561	6569	928871	843911	832457	379343	2351	42299	964199	1439	2207	217499	427073	73433	770873	170123	11000000
951389	984119	556709	998633	705821	996881	87149	617237	748883	842159	578441	975581	17939	40277	216401	875933	3119	294179	1367	443291	15881	48611	11000000
994769	995747	997121	999239	942779	390491	807383	681839	753527	826571	866123	539171	163883	51419	3677	24917	890999	57221	761	2879	4253	5231	11000000
999863	999491	998681	999521	876677	850133	935339	778397	976643	918767	854033	110063	98867	57251	225509	94547	23117	200657	479	1319	509	137	11000000
999917	999749	992513	823799	577547	718007	801341	835013	845387	569573	852623	539663	642011	84377	30137	9677	84131	2411	584303	7487	251	83	11000000
999959	999809	757553	631061	617537	680189	912089	519413	532739	691949	576743	594953	527753	920399	150083	44687	20939	20789	227	800897	191	41	11000000
999599	702809	880553	644201	926669	695369	623291	955481	930089	818561	749249	707573	32237	651647	28439	2039	147761	21179	3539	30071	449243	401	11000000
474983	838247	760301	984329	712133	500321	587711	733847	933839	561047	873317	876797	873641	313661	32771	20051	173651	26849	10091	569	971	710873	11000000
11000000	11000000	11000000	11000000	11000000	11000000	11000000	11000000	11000000	11000000	11000000	11000000	11000000	11000000	11000000	11000000	11000000	11000000	11000000	11000000	11000000	11000000	11000000

It contains the prime magic squares of orders 4, 6, 8, 10, 12, 14, 16, 18 and 20 given above. All the primes are distinct.

2.11 Prime Magic Square of Order 24

24	mgc																					12000000			
	709817	54101	467549	94379	470651	13187	488981	218783	482519	304757	403757	142421	184721	354581	430799	440087	836807	954509	997889	951407	994199	995927	996539	11633	12000000
	395189	289127	161753	239699	15671	287867	499679	412289	266153	66161	438953	126683	123203	126359	686339	967229	979949	826349	973151	989909	999431	999029	525017	604811	12000000
	301583	496841	550757	119447	355799	73331	304631	376709	44519	69911	181439	250751	292427	967763	348353	971561	997961	852239	978821	996461	969929	297191	503159	698417	12000000
	114041	77783	211811	199103	368939	382463	319811	87911	480587	467261	308051	423257	405047	472247	79601	849917	955313	979061	979211	999773	242447	788189	922217	885959	12000000
	239711	335417	253823	247799	415697	422453	281993	198659	164987	154613	430427	147377	460337	357989	915623	969863	990323	915869	997589	176201	752201	746177	664583	760289	12000000
	123407	21383	275921	255083	212183	799343	149867	64661	221603	23357	81233	145967	889937	901133	942749	774491	905453	976883	123323	787817	744917	724079	978617	876593	12000000
	493001	302873	58229	341057	423209	54269	109001	192617	318161	246473	173429	133877	460829	836117	948581	996323	975083	609509	945731	576791	658943	941771	697127	506999	12000000
	208889	149519	330689	362291	274019	352349	22643	124067	382763	251117	157841	421559	24419	982061	959723	783599	912851	977357	647651	725981	637709	669311	850481	791111	12000000
	478637	182681	172259	354479	238991	113489	70997	19841	35801	71129	156089	167543	620657	997649	957701	993431	980159	929003	886511	761009	645521	827741	817319	521363	12000000
	70439	428411	151703	299567	14723	266177	352511	157721	466073	881591	86783	124739	940271	457889	508727	533927	842279	647489	733823	985277	700433	848297	571589	929561	12000000
	98573	109541	304553	31091	163847	30539	120299	364433	29201	149057	306191	65951	934049	693809	850943	970799	635567	879701	969461	836153	968909	695447	890459	901427	12000000
	311237	48869	341597	89381	41513	2903	65921	447683	979373	194963	878651	799619	200381	121349	805037	20627	552317	934079	997097	958487	910619	658403	951131	688763	12000000
	94049	91529	400523	282011	12413	277757	989939	804191	790379	349709	517901	808553	191447	482099	650291	209621	195809	10061	722243	987587	717989	599477	908471	905951	12000000
	480419	222269	125201	441527	876077	982769	919823	997973	919067	933407	297257	325877	674123	702743	66593	80933	2027	80177	17231	123923	558473	874799	777731	519581	12000000
	310043	993401	912083	867467	933209	812627	963701	998381	773537	491273	913217	875261	59729	542111	118409	226463	1619	36299	187373	66791	132533	87917	6599	689957	12000000
	438233	829877	229127	926567	572927	782501	997793	998561	6569	928871	843911	832457	379343	2351	42299	964199	1439	2207	217499	427073	73433	770873	170123	561767	12000000
	287501	951389	984119	556709	998633	705821	996881	87149	617237	748883	842159	578441	975581	17939	40277	216401	875933	3119	294179	1367	443291	15881	48611	712499	12000000
	904847	994769	995747	997121	999239	942779	390491	807383	681839	753527	826571	866123	539171	163883	51419	3677	24917	890999	57221	761	2879	4253	5231	95153	12000000
	987083	999863	999491	998681	999521	876677	850133	935339	778397	976643	918767	854033	110063	98867	57251	225509	94547	23117	200657	479	1319	509	137	12917	12000000
	989687	999917	999749	992513	823799	577547	718007	801341	835013	845387	569573	852623	539663	642011	84377	30137	9677	84131	2411	584303	7487	251	83	10313	12000000
	994013	999959	999809	757553	631061	617537	680189	912089	519413	532739	691949	576743	594953	527753	920399	150083	44687	20939	20789	227	800897	191	41	5987	12000000
	992891	999599	702809	880553	644201	926669	695369	623291	955481	930089	818561	749249	707573	32237	651647	28439	2039	147761	21179	3539	30071	449243	401	7109	12000000
	988343	474983	838247	760301	984329	712133	500321	587711	733847	933839	561047	873317	876797	873641	313661	32771	20051	173651	26849	10091	569	971	710873	11657	12000000
	988367	945899	532451	905621	529349	986813	511019	781217	517481	695243	596243	857579	815279	645419	569201	559913	163193	45491	2111	48593	5801	4073	3461	290183	12000000
	12000000	12000000	12000000	12000000	12000000	12000000	12000000	12000000	12000000	12000000	12000000	12000000	12000000	12000000	12000000	12000000	12000000	12000000	12000000	12000000	12000000	12000000	12000000	12000000	12000000

It contains the prime magic squares of orders 4, 6, 8, 10, 12, 14, 16, 18, 20 and 22 given above. All the primes are distinct.

2.12 Prime Magic Square of Order 26

26	mgc																								13000000	
252401	398249	321617	163733	336761	145829	168347	494927	63131	481673	249881	379187	449759	448907	390113	159389	83813	990797	954869	933551	974417	985379	997391	999983	999683	176213	13000000
471281	709817	54101	467549	94379	470651	13187	488981	218783	482519	304757	403757	142421	184721	354581	430799	440087	836807	954509	997889	951407	994199	995927	996539	11633	528719	13000000
188417	395189	289127	161753	239699	15671	287867	499679	412289	266153	66161	438953	126683	123203	126359	686339	967229	979949	826349	973151	989909	999431	999029	525017	604811	811583	13000000
69491	301583	496841	550757	119447	355799	73331	304631	376709	44519	69911	181439	250751	292427	967763	348353	971561	997961	852239	978821	996461	969929	297191	503159	698417	930509	13000000
130223	114041	77783	211811	199103	368939	382463	319811	87911	480587	467261	308051	423257	405047	472247	79601	849917	955313	979061	979211	999773	242447	788189	922217	885959	869777	13000000
150869	239711	335417	253823	247799	415697	422453	281993	198659	164987	154613	430427	147377	460337	357989	915623	969863	990323	915869	997589	176201	752201	746177	664583	760289	849131	13000000
326549	123407	21383	275921	255083	212183	799343	149867	64661	221603	23357	81233	145967	889937	901133	942749	774491	905453	976883	123323	787817	744917	724079	978617	876593	673451	13000000
436979	493001	302873	58229	341057	423209	54269	109001	192617	318161	246473	173429	133877	460829	836117	948581	996323	975083	609509	945731	576791	658943	941771	697127	506999	563021	13000000
218117	208889	149519	330689	362291	274019	352349	22643	124067	382763	251117	157841	421559	24419	982061	959723	783599	912851	977357	647651	725981	637709	669311	850481	791111	781883	13000000
121403	478637	182681	172259	354479	238991	113489	70997	19841	35801	71129	156089	167543	620657	997649	957701	993431	980159	929003	886511	761009	645521	827741	817319	521363	878597	13000000
39869	70439	428411	151703	299567	14723	266177	352511	157721	466073	881591	86783	124739	940271	457889	508727	533927	842279	647489	733823	985277	700433	848297	571589	929561	960131	13000000
140333	98573	109541	304553	31091	163847	30539	120299	364433	29201	149057	306191	65951	934049	693809	850943	970799	635567	879701	969461	836153	968909	695447	890459	901427	859667	13000000
41957	311237	48869	341597	89381	41513	2903	65921	447683	979373	194963	878651	799619	200381	121349	805037	20627	552317	934079	997097	958487	910619	658403	951131	688763	958043	13000000
80681	94049	91529	400523	282011	12413	277757	989939	804191	790379	349709	517901	808553	191447	482099	650291	209621	195809	10061	722243	987587	717989	599477	908471	905951	919319	13000000
428951	480419	222269	125201	441527	876077	982769	919823	997973	919067	933407	297257	325877	674123	702743	66593	80933	2027	80177	17231	123923	558473	874799	777731	519581	571049	13000000
490277	310043	993401	912083	867467	933209	812627	963701	998381	773537	491273	913217	875261	59729	542111	118409	226463	1619	36299	187373	66791	132533	87917	6599	689957	509723	13000000
926027	438233	829877	229127	926567	572927	782501	997793	998561	6569	928871	843911	832457	379343	2351	42299	964199	1439	2207	217499	427073	73433	770873	170123	561767	73973	13000000
754739	287501	951389	984119	556709	998633	705821	996881	87149	617237	748883	842159	578441	975581	17939	40277	216401	875933	3119	294179	1367	443291	15881	48611	712499	245261	13000000
948551	904847	994769	995747	997121	999239	942779	390491	807383	681839	753527	826571	866123	539171	163883	51419	3677	24917	890999	57221	761	2879	4253	5231	95153	51449	13000000
976187	987083	999863	999491	998681	999521	876677	850133	935339	778397	976643	918767	854033	110063	98867	57251	225509	94547	23117	200657	479	1319	509	137	12917	23813	13000000
996329	989687	999917	999749	992513	823799	577547	718007	801341	835013	845387	569573	852623	539663	642011	84377	30137	9677	84131	2411	584303	7487	251	83	10313	3671	13000000
998969	994013	999959	999809	757553	631061	617537	680189	912089	519413	532739	691949	576743	594953	527753	920399	150083	44687	20939	20789	227	800897	191	41	5987	1031	13000000
991217	992891	999599	702809	880553	644201	926669	695369	623291	955481	930089	818561	749249	707573	32237	651647	28439	2039	147761	21179	3539	30071	449243	401	7109	8783	13000000
999359	988343	474983	838247	760301	984329	712133	500321	587711	733847	933839	561047	873317	876797	873641	313661	32771	20051	173651	26849	10091	569	971	710873	11657	641	13000000
997037	988367	945899	532451	905621	529349	986813	511019	781217	517481	695243	596243	857579	815279	645419	569201	559913	163193	45491	2111	48593	5801	4073	3461	290183	2963	13000000
823787	601751	678383	836267	663239	854171	831653	505073	936869	518327	750119	620813	550241	551093	609887	840611	916187	9203	45131	66449	25583	14621	2609	17	317	747599	13000000
13000000	13000000	13000000	13000000	13000000	13000000	13000000	13000000	13000000	13000000	13000000	13000000	13000000	13000000	13000000	13000000	13000000	13000000	13000000	13000000	13000000	13000000	13000000	13000000	13000000	13000000	13000000

It contains the prime magic squares of orders 4, 6, 8, 10, 12, 14, 16, 18, 20, 22 and 24 given above. All the primes are distinct.

2.13 Prime Magic Square of Order 28

28	mgc																											14000000
526781	433319	353747	287933	286733	216731	161453	393551	413429	152183	356561	152753	313949	154691	457397	196187	325043	491159	491201	287669	754037	980921	994901	998909	999653	999611	998819	820679	14000000
418739	252401	398249	321617	163733	336761	145829	168347	494927	63131	481673	249881	379187	449759	448907	390113	159389	83813	990797	954869	933551	974417	985379	997391	999983	999683	176213	581261	14000000
329789	471281	709817	54101	467549	94379	470651	13187	488981	218783	482519	304757	403757	142421	184721	354581	430799	440087	836807	954509	997889	951407	994199	995927	996539	11633	528719	670211	14000000
467147	188417	395189	289127	161753	239699	15671	287867	499679	412289	266153	66161	438953	126683	123203	126359	686339	967229	979949	826349	973151	989909	999431	999029	525017	604811	811583	532853	14000000
419999	69491	301583	496841	550757	119447	355799	73331	304631	376709	44519	69911	181439	250751	292427	967763	348353	971561	997961	852239	978821	996461	969929	297191	503159	698417	930509	580001	14000000
43013	130223	114041	77783	211811	199103	368939	382463	319811	87911	480587	467261	308051	423257	405047	472247	79601	849917	955313	979061	979211	999773	242447	788189	922217	885959	869777	956987	14000000
122399	150869	239711	335417	253823	247799	415697	422453	281993	198659	164987	154613	430427	147377	460337	357989	915623	969863	990323	915869	997589	176201	752201	746177	664583	760289	849131	877601	14000000
144779	326549	123407	21383	275921	255083	212183	799343	149867	64661	221603	23357	81233	145967	889937	901133	942749	774491	905453	976883	123323	787817	744917	724079	978617	876593	673451	855221	14000000
135893	436979	493001	302873	58229	341057	423209	54269	109001	192617	318161	246473	173429	133877	460829	836117	948581	996323	975083	609509	945731	576791	658943	941771	697127	506999	563021	864107	14000000
365357	218117	208889	149519	330689	362291	274019	352349	22643	124067	382763	251117	157841	421559	24419	982061	959723	783599	912851	977357	647651	725981	637709	669311	850481	791111	781883	634643	14000000
108233	121403	478637	182681	172259	354479	238991	113489	70997	19841	35801	71129	156089	167543	620657	997649	957701	993431	980159	929003	886511	761009	645521	827741	817319	521363	878597	891767	14000000
60251	39869	70439	428411	151703	299567	14723	266177	352511	157721	466073	881591	86783	124739	940271	457889	508727	533927	842279	647489	733823	985277	700433	848297	571589	929561	960131	939749	14000000
247067	140333	98573	109541	304553	31091	163847	30539	120299	364433	29201	149057	306191	65951	934049	693809	850943	970799	635567	879701	969461	836153	968909	695447	890459	901427	859667	752933	14000000
157733	41957	311237	48869	341597	89381	41513	2903	65921	447683	979373	194963	878651	799619	200381	121349	805037	20627	552317	934079	997097	958487	910619	658403	951131	688763	958043	842267	14000000
354143	80681	94049	91529	400523	282011	12413	277757	989939	804191	790379	349709	517901	808553	191447	482099	650291	209621	195809	10061	722243	987587	717989	599477	908471	905951	919319	645857	14000000
414347	428951	480419	222269	125201	441527	876077	982769	919823	997973	919067	933407	297257	325877	674123	702743	66593	80933	2027	80177	17231	123923	558473	874799	777731	519581	571049	585653	14000000
306149	490277	310043	993401	912083	867467	933209	812627	963701	998381	773537	491273	913217	875261	59729	542111	118409	226463	1619	36299	187373	66791	132533	87917	6599	689957	509723	693851	14000000
420191	926027	438233	829877	229127	926567	572927	782501	997793	998561	6569	928871	843911	832457	379343	2351	42299	964199	1439	2207	217499	427073	73433	770873	170123	561767	73973	579809	14000000
814937	754739	287501	951389	984119	556709	998633	705821	996881	87149	617237	748883	842159	578441	975581	17939	40277	216401	875933	3119	294179	1367	443291	15881	48611	712499	245261	185063	14000000
997343	948551	904847	994769	995747	997121	999239	942779	390491	807383	681839	753527	826571	866123	539171	163883	51419	3677	24917	890999	57221	761	2879	4253	5231	95153	51449	2657	14000000
996119	976187	987083	999863	999491	998681	999521	876677	850133	935339	778397	976643	918767	854033	110063	98867	57251	225509	94547	23117	200657	479	1319	509	137	12917	23813	3881	14000000
997043	996329	989687	999917	999749	992513	823799	577547	718007	801341	835013	845387	569573	852623	539663	642011	84377	30137	9677	84131	2411	584303	7487	251	83	10313	3671	2957	14000000
993827	998969	994013	999959	999809	757553	631061	617537	680189	912089	519413	532739	691949	576743	594953	527753	920399	150083	44687	20939	20789	227	800897	191	41	5987	1031	6173	14000000
988607	991217	992891	999599	702809	880553	644201	926669	695369	623291	955481	930089	818561	749249	707573	32237	651647	28439	2039	147761	21179	3539	30071	449243	401	7109	8783	11393	14000000
994949	999359	988343	474983	838247	760301	984329	712133	500321	587711	733847	933839	561047	873317	876797	873641	313661	32771	20051	173651	26849	10091	569	971	710873	11657	641	5051	14000000
996407	997037	988367	945899	532451	905621	529349	986813	511019	781217	517481	695243	596243	857579	815279	645419	569201	559913	163193	45491	2111	48593	5801	4073	3461	290183	2963	3593	14000000
999437	823787	601751	678383	836267	663239	854171	831653	505073	936869	518327	750119	620813	550241	551093	609887	840611	916187	9203	45131	66449	25583	14621	2609	17	317	747599	563	14000000
179321	566681	646253	712067	713267	783269	838547	606449	586571	847817	643439	847247	686051	845309	542603	803813	674957	508841	508799	712331	245963	19079	5099	1091	347	389	1181	473219	14000000
14000000	14000000	14000000	14000000	14000000	14000000	14000000	14000000	14000000	14000000	14000000	14000000	14000000	14000000	14000000	14000000	14000000	14000000	14000000	14000000	14000000	14000000	14000000	14000000	14000000	14000000	14000000	14000000	14000000

It contains the prime magic squares of orders 4, 6, 8, 10, 12, 14, 16, 18, 20, 22, 24 and 26 given above. All the primes are distinct.

2.14 Prime Magic Square of Order 30

30	mgc																													15000000
706793	478343	8111	362717	376463	326219	31727	398369	46349	170243	377291	237179	53147	165203	173981	260609	236087	58391	995327	860921	667013	895463	939971	984587	992549	996197	995591	998513	997379	209267	15000000
91457	526781	433319	353747	287933	286733	216731	161453	393551	413429	152183	356561	152753	313949	154691	457397	196187	325043	491159	491201	287669	754037	980921	994901	998909	999653	999611	998819	820679	908543	15000000
228113	418739	252401	398249	321617	163733	336761	145829	168347	494927	63131	481673	249881	379187	449759	448907	390113	159389	83813	990797	954869	933551	974417	985379	997391	999983	999683	176213	581261	771887	15000000
485351	329789	471281	709817	54101	467549	94379	470651	13187	488981	218783	482519	304757	403757	142421	184721	354581	430799	440087	836807	954509	997889	951407	994199	995927	996539	11633	528719	670211	514649	15000000
208049	467147	188417	395189	289127	161753	239699	15671	287867	499679	412289	266153	66161	438953	126683	123203	126359	686339	967229	979949	826349	973151	989909	999431	999029	525017	604811	811583	532853	791951	15000000
334619	419999	69491	301583	496841	550757	119447	355799	73331	304631	376709	44519	69911	181439	250751	292427	967763	348353	971561	997961	852239	978821	996461	969929	297191	503159	698417	930509	580001	665381	15000000
241259	43013	130223	114041	77783	211811	199103	368939	382463	319811	87911	480587	467261	308051	423257	405047	472247	79601	849917	955313	979061	979211	999773	242447	788189	922217	885959	869777	956987	758741	15000000
335579	122399	150869	239711	335417	253823	247799	415697	422453	281993	198659	164987	154613	430427	147377	460337	357989	915623	969863	990323	915869	997589	176201	752201	746177	664583	760289	849131	877601	664421	15000000
24677	144779	326549	123407	21383	275921	255083	212183	799343	149867	64661	221603	23357	81233	145967	889937	901133	942749	774491	905453	976883	123323	787817	744917	724079	978617	876593	673451	855221	975323	15000000
181031	135893	436979	493001	302873	58229	341057	423209	54269	109001	192617	318161	246473	173429	133877	460829	836117	948581	996323	975083	609509	945731	576791	658943	941771	697127	506999	563021	864107	818969	15000000
128483	365357	218117	208889	149519	330689	362291	274019	352349	22643	124067	382763	251117	157841	421559	24419	982061	959723	783599	912851	977357	647651	725981	637709	669311	850481	791111	781883	634643	871517	15000000
365021	108233	121403	478637	182681	172259	354479	238991	113489	70997	19841	35801	71129	156089	167543	620657	997649	957701	993431	980159	929003	886511	761009	645521	827741	817319	521363	878597	891767	634979	15000000
18059	60251	39869	70439	428411	151703	299567	14723	266177	352511	157721	466073	881591	86783	124739	940271	457889	508727	533927	842279	647489	733823	985277	700433	848297	571589	929561	960131	939749	981941	15000000
412571	247067	140333	98573	109541	304553	31091	163847	30539	120299	364433	29201	149057	306191	65951	934049	693809	850943	970799	635567	879701	969461	836153	968909	695447	890459	901427	859667	752933	587429	15000000
30203	157733	41957	311237	48869	341597	89381	41513	2903	65921	447683	979373	194963	878651	799619	200381	121349	805037	20627	552317	934079	997097	958487	910619	658403	951131	688763	958043	842267	969797	15000000
481379	354143	80681	94049	91529	400523	282011	12413	277757	989939	804191	790379	349709	517901	808553	191447	482099	650291	209621	195809	10061	722243	987587	717989	599477	908471	905951	919319	645857	518621	15000000
196073	414347	428951	480419	222269	125201	441527	876077	982769	919823	997973	919067	933407	297257	325877	674123	702743	66593	80933	2027	80177	17231	123923	558473	874799	777731	519581	571049	585653	803927	15000000
407861	306149	490277	310043	993401	912083	867467	933209	812627	963701	998381	773537	491273	913217	875261	59729	542111	118409	226463	1619	36299	187373	66791	132533	87917	6599	689957	509723	693851	592139	15000000
56591	420191	926027	438233	829877	229127	926567	572927	782501	997793	998561	6569	928871	843911	832457	379343	2351	42299	964199	1439	2207	217499	427073	73433	770873	170123	561767	73973	579809	943409	15000000
880871	814937	754739	287501	951389	984119	556709	998633	705821	996881	87149	617237	748883	842159	578441	975581	17939	40277	216401	875933	3119	294179	1367	443291	15881	48611	712499	245261	185063	119129	15000000
723551	997343	948551	904847	994769	995747	997121	999239	942779	390491	807383	681839	753527	826571	866123	539171	163883	51419	3677	24917	890999	57221	761	2879	4253	5231	95153	51449	2657	276449	15000000
767153	996119	976187	987083	999863	999491	998681	999521	876677	850133	935339	778397	976643	918767	854033	110063	98867	57251	225509	94547	23117	200657	479	1319	509	137	12917	23813	3881	232847	15000000
934343	997043	996329	989687	999917	999749	992513	823799	577547	718007	801341	835013	845387	569573	852623	539663	642011	84377	30137	9677	84131	2411	584303	7487	251	83	10313	3671	2957	65657	15000000
994583	993827	998969	994013	999959	999809	757553	631061	617537	680189	912089	519413	532739	691949	576743	594953	527753	920399	150083	44687	20939	20789	227	800897	191	41	5987	1031	6173	5417	15000000
997727	988607	991217	992891	999599	702809	880553	644201	926669	695369	623291	955481	930089	818561	749249	707573	32237	651647	28439	2039	147761	21179	3539	30071	449243	401	7109	8783	11393	2273	15000000
995909	994949	999359	988343	474983	838247	760301	984329	712133	500321	587711	733847	933839	561047	873317	876797	873641	313661	32771	20051	173651	26849	10091	569	971	710873	11657	641	5051	4091	15000000
985679	996407	997037	988367	945899	532451	905621	529349	986813	511019	781217	517481	695243	596243	857579	815279	645419	569201	559913	163193	45491	2111	48593	5801	4073	3461	290183	2963	3593	14321	15000000
999023	999437	823787	601751	678383	836267	663239	854171	831653	505073	936869	518327	750119	620813	550241	551093	609887	840611	916187	9203	45131	66449	25583	14621	2609	17	317	747599	563	977	15000000
997259	179321	566681	646253	712067	713267	783269	838547	606449	586571	847817	643439	847247	686051	845309	542603	803813	674957	508841	508799	712331	245963	19079	5099	1091	347	389	1181	473219	2741	15000000
790733	521657	991889	637283	623537	673781	968273	601631	953651	829757	622709	762821	946853	834797	826019	739391	763913	941609	4673	139079	332987	104537	60029	15413	7451	3803	4409	1487	2621	293207	15000000
15000000	15000000	15000000	15000000	15000000	15000000	15000000	15000000	15000000	15000000	15000000	15000000	15000000	15000000	15000000	15000000	15000000	15000000	15000000	15000000	15000000	15000000	15000000	15000000	15000000	15000000	15000000	15000000	15000000	15000000	15000000

It contains the prime magic squares of orders 4, 6, 8, 10, 12, 14, 16, 18, 20, 22, 24, 26 and 28 given above. All the primes are distinct.

2.15 Prime Magic Square of Order 32

331967	144539	12071	274103	406013	419591	92669	457517	283553	460793	329177	394211	286043	322319	307337	240869	487073	334889	224909	31973	310781	492257	759491	940547	950333	987599	969989	991427	997307	990761	982343	785549
319343	706793	478343	8111	362717	376463	326219	31727	398369	46349	170243	377291	237179	53147	165203	173981	260609	236087	58391	995327	860921	667013	895463	939971	984587	992549	996197	995591	998513	997379	209267	680657
52517	91457	526781	433319	353747	287933	286733	216731	161453	393551	413429	152183	356561	152753	313949	154691	457397	196187	325043	491159	491201	287669	754037	980921	994901	998909	999653	999611	998819	820679	908543	947483
438611	228113	418739	252401	398249	321617	163733	336761	145829	168347	494927	63131	481673	249881	379187	449759	448907	390113	159389	83813	990797	954869	933551	974417	985379	997391	999983	999683	176213	581261	771887	561389
115679	485351	329789	471281	709817	54101	467549	94379	470651	13187	488981	218783	482519	304757	403757	142421	184721	354581	430799	440087	836807	954509	997889	951407	994199	995927	996539	11633	528719	670211	514649	884321
363977	208049	467147	188417	395189	289127	161753	239699	15671	287867	499679	412289	266153	66161	438953	126683	123203	126359	686339	967229	979949	826349	973151	989909	999431	999029	525017	604811	811583	532853	791951	636023
222863	334619	419999	69491	301583	496841	550757	119447	355799	73331	304631	376709	44519	69911	181439	250751	292427	967763	348353	971561	997961	852239	978821	996461	969929	297191	503159	698417	930509	580001	665381	777137
382661	241259	43013	130223	114041	77783	211811	199103	368939	382463	319811	87911	480587	467261	308051	423257	405047	472247	79601	849917	955313	979061	979211	999773	242447	788189	922217	885959	869777	956987	758741	617339
26177	335579	122399	150869	239711	335417	253823	247799	415697	422453	281993	198659	164987	154613	430427	147377	460337	357989	915623	969863	990323	915869	997589	176201	752201	746177	664583	760289	849131	877601	664421	973823
254963	24677	144779	326549	123407	21383	275921	255083	212183	799343	149867	64661	221603	23357	81233	145967	889937	901133	942749	774491	905453	976883	123323	787817	744917	724079	978617	876593	673451	855221	975323	745037
363149	181031	135893	436979	493001	302873	58229	341057	423209	54269	109001	192617	318161	246473	173429	133877	460829	836117	948581	996323	975083	609509	945731	576791	658943	941771	697127	506999	563021	864107	818969	636851
320081	128483	365357	218117	208889	149519	330689	362291	274019	352349	22643	124067	382763	251117	157841	421559	24419	982061	959723	783599	912851	977357	647651	725981	637709	669311	850481	791111	781883	634643	871517	679919
33107	365021	108233	121403	478637	182681	172259	354479	238991	113489	70997	19841	35801	71129	156089	167543	620657	997649	957701	993431	980159	929003	886511	761009	645521	827741	817319	521363	878597	891767	634979	966893
491039	18059	60251	39869	70439	428411	151703	299567	14723	266177	352511	157721	466073	881591	86783	124739	940271	457889	508727	533927	842279	647489	733823	985277	700433	848297	571589	929561	960131	939749	981941	508961
270797	412571	247067	140333	98573	109541	304553	31091	163847	30539	120299	364433	29201	149057	306191	65951	934049	693809	850943	970799	635567	879701	969461	836153	968909	695447	890459	901427	859667	752933	587429	729203
471959	30203	157733	41957	311237	48869	341597	89381	41513	2903	65921	447683	979373	194963	878651	799619	200381	121349	805037	20627	552317	934079	997097	958487	910619	658403	951131	688763	958043	842267	969797	528041
295313	481379	354143	80681	94049	91529	400523	282011	12413	277757	989939	804191	790379	349709	517901	808553	191447	482099	650291	209621	195809	10061	722243	987587	717989	599477	908471	905951	919319	645857	518621	704687
143609	196073	414347	428951	480419	222269	125201	441527	876077	982769	919823	997973	919067	933407	297257	325877	674123	702743	66593	80933	2027	80177	17231	123923	558473	874799	777731	519581	571049	585653	803927	856391
413027	407861	306149	490277	310043	993401	912083	867467	933209	812627	963701	998381	773537	491273	913217	875261	59729	542111	118409	226463	1619	36299	187373	66791	132533	87917	6599	689957	509723	693851	592139	586973
6221	56591	420191	926027	438233	829877	229127	926567	572927	782501	997793	998561	6569	928871	843911	832457	379343	2351	42299	964199	1439	2207	217499	427073	73433	770873	170123	561767	73973	579809	943409	993779
784313	880871	814937	754739	287501	951389	984119	556709	998633	705821	996881	87149	617237	748883	842159	578441	975581	17939	40277	216401	875933	3119	294179	1367	443291	15881	48611	712499	245261	185063	119129	215687
989921	723551	997343	948551	904847	994769	995747	997121	999239	942779	390491	807383	681839	753527	826571	866123	539171	163883	51419	3677	24917	890999	57221	761	2879	4253	5231	95153	51449	2657	276449	10079
915947	767153	996119	976187	987083	999863	999491	998681	999521	876677	850133	935339	778397	976643	918767	854033	110063	98867	57251	225509	94547	23117	200657	479	1319	509	137	12917	23813	3881	232847	84053
860759	934343	997043	996329	989687	999917	999749	992513	823799	577547	718007	801341	835013	845387	569573	852623	539663	642011	84377	30137	9677	84131	2411	584303	7487	251	83	10313	3671	2957	65657	139241
985631	994583	993827	998969	994013	999959	999809	757553	631061	617537	680189	912089	519413	532739	691949	576743	594953	527753	920399	150083	44687	20939	20789	227	800897	191	41	5987	1031	6173	5417	14369
996011	997727	988607	991217	992891	999599	702809	880553	644201	926669	695369	623291	955481	930089	818561	749249	707573	32237	651647	28439	2039	147761	21179	3539	30071	449243	401	7109	8783	11393	2273	3989
976211	995909	994949	999359	988343	474983	838247	760301	984329	712133	500321	587711	733847	933839	561047	873317	876797	873641	313661	32771	20051	173651	26849	10091	569	971	710873	11657	641	5051	4091	23789
994559	985679	996407	997037	988367	945899	532451	905621	529349	986813	511019	781217	517481	695243	596243	857579	815279	645419	569201	559913	163193	45491	2111	48593	5801	4073	3461	290183	2963	3593	14321	5441
976439	999023	999437	823787	601751	678383	836267	663239	854171	831653	505073	936869	518327	750119	620813	550241	551093	609887	840611	916187	9203	45131	66449	25583	14621	2609	17	317	747599	563	977	23561
993887	997259	179321	566681	646253	712067	713267	783269	838547	606449	586571	847817	643439	847247	686051	845309	542603	803813	674957	508841	508799	712331	245963	19079	5099	1091	347	389	1181	473219	2741	6113
994811	790733	521657	991889	637283	623537	673781	968273	601631	953651	829757	622709	762821	946853	834797	826019	739391	763913	941609	4673	139079	332987	104537	60029	15413	7451	3803	4409	1487	2621	293207	5189
214451	855461	987929	725897	593987	580409	907331	542483	716447	539207	670823	605789	713957	677681	692663	759131	512927	665111	775091	968027	689219	507743	240509	59453	49667	12401	30011	8573	2693	9239	17657	668033

It contains the prime magic squares of orders 4, 6, 8, 10, 12, 14, 16, 18, 20, 22, 24, 26, 28 and 30 given above. All the primes are distinct.

2.16 Prime Magic Square of Order 34

842477	157181	423341	258197	301979	9497	331259	411479	311567	142097	220511	410507	282809	138563	251177	44729	454253	30593	11273	228539	275153	872237	983579	973367	788993	883451	751943	942653	975389	994667	994193	998213	998897	305237
856169	331967	144539	12071	274103	406013	419591	92669	457517	283553	460793	329177	394211	286043	322319	307337	240869	487073	334889	224909	31973	310781	492257	759491	940547	950333	987599	969989	991427	997307	990761	982343	785549	143831
46829	319343	706793	478343	8111	362717	376463	326219	31727	398369	46349	170243	377291	237179	53147	165203	173981	260609	236087	58391	995327	860921	667013	895463	939971	984587	992549	996197	995591	998513	997379	209267	680657	953171
609047	52517	91457	526781	433319	353747	287933	286733	216731	161453	393551	413429	152183	356561	152753	313949	154691	457397	196187	325043	491159	491201	287669	754037	980921	994901	998909	999653	999611	998819	820679	908543	947483	390953
943403	438611	228113	418739	252401	398249	321617	163733	336761	145829	168347	494927	63131	481673	249881	379187	449759	448907	390113	159389	83813	990797	954869	933551	974417	985379	997391	999983	999683	176213	581261	771887	561389	56597
195311	115679	485351	329789	471281	709817	54101	467549	94379	470651	13187	488981	218783	482519	304757	403757	142421	184721	354581	430799	440087	836807	954509	997889	951407	994199	995927	996539	11633	528719	670211	514649	884321	804689
970667	363977	208049	467147	188417	395189	289127	161753	239699	15671	287867	499679	412289	266153	66161	438953	126683	123203	126359	686339	967229	979949	826349	973151	989909	999431	999029	525017	604811	811583	532853	791951	636023	29333
70139	222863	334619	419999	69491	301583	496841	550757	119447	355799	73331	304631	376709	44519	69911	181439	250751	292427	967763	348353	971561	997961	852239	978821	996461	969929	297191	503159	698417	930509	580001	665381	777137	929861
356351	382661	241259	43013	130223	114041	77783	211811	199103	368939	382463	319811	87911	480587	467261	308051	423257	405047	472247	79601	849917	955313	979061	979211	999773	242447	788189	922217	885959	869777	956987	758741	617339	643649
386549	26177	335579	122399	150869	239711	335417	253823	247799	415697	422453	281993	198659	164987	154613	430427	147377	460337	357989	915623	969863	990323	915869	997589	176201	752201	746177	664583	760289	849131	877601	664421	973823	613451
48779	254963	24677	144779	326549	123407	21383	275921	255083	212183	799343	149867	64661	221603	23357	81233	145967	889937	901133	942749	774491	905453	976883	123323	787817	744917	724079	978617	876593	673451	855221	975323	745037	951221
768401	363149	181031	135893	436979	493001	302873	58229	341057	423209	54269	109001	192617	318161	246473	173429	133877	460829	836117	948581	996323	975083	609509	945731	576791	658943	941771	697127	506999	563021	864107	818969	636851	231599
597473	320081	128483	365357	218117	208889	149519	330689	362291	274019	352349	22643	124067	382763	251117	157841	421559	24419	982061	959723	783599	912851	977357	647651	725981	637709	669311	850481	791111	781883	634643	871517	679919	402527
853949	33107	365021	108233	121403	478637	182681	172259	354479	238991	113489	70997	19841	35801	71129	156089	167543	620657	997649	957701	993431	980159	929003	886511	761009	645521	827741	817319	521363	878597	891767	634979	966893	146051
960581	491039	18059	60251	39869	70439	428411	151703	299567	14723	266177	352511	157721	466073	881591	86783	124739	940271	457889	508727	533927	842279	647489	733823	985277	700433	848297	571589	929561	960131	939749	981941	508961	39419
848843	270797	412571	247067	140333	98573	109541	304553	31091	163847	30539	120299	364433	29201	149057	306191	65951	934049	693809	850943	970799	635567	879701	969461	836153	968909	695447	890459	901427	859667	752933	587429	729203	151157
416579	471959	30203	157733	41957	311237	48869	341597	89381	41513	2903	65921	447683	979373	194963	878651	799619	200381	121349	805037	20627	552317	934079	997097	958487	910619	658403	951131	688763	958043	842267	969797	528041	583421
423251	295313	481379	354143	80681	94049	91529	400523	282011	12413	277757	989939	804191	790379	349709	517901	808553	191447	482099	650291	209621	195809	10061	722243	987587	717989	599477	908471	905951	919319	645857	518621	704687	576749
24329	143609	196073	414347	428951	480419	222269	125201	441527	876077	982769	919823	997973	919067	933407	297257	325877	674123	702743	66593	80933	2027	80177	17231	123923	558473	874799	777731	519581	571049	585653	803927	856391	975671
777863	413027	407861	306149	490277	310043	993401	912083	867467	933209	812627	963701	998381	773537	491273	913217	875261	59729	542111	118409	226463	1619	36299	187373	66791	132533	87917	6599	689957	509723	693851	592139	586973	222137
41453	6221	56591	420191	926027	438233	829877	229127	926567	572927	782501	997793	998561	6569	928871	843911	832457	379343	2351	42299	964199	1439	2207	217499	427073	73433	770873	170123	561767	73973	579809	943409	993779	958547
277637	784313	880871	814937	754739	287501	951389	984119	556709	998633	705821	996881	87149	617237	748883	842159	578441	975581	17939	40277	216401	875933	3119	294179	1367	443291	15881	48611	712499	245261	185063	119129	215687	722363
921287	989921	723551	997343	948551	904847	994769	995747	997121	999239	942779	390491	807383	681839	753527	826571	866123	539171	163883	51419	3677	24917	890999	57221	761	2879	4253	5231	95153	51449	2657	276449	10079	78713
634871	915947	767153	996119	976187	987083	999863	999491	998681	999521	876677	850133	935339	778397	976643	918767	854033	110063	98867	57251	225509	94547	23117	200657	479	1319	509	137	12917	23813	3881	232847	84053	365129
215351	860759	934343	997043	996329	989687	999917	999749	992513	823799	577547	718007	801341	835013	845387	569573	852623	539663	642011	84377	30137	9677	84131	2411	584303	7487	251	83	10313	3671	2957	65657	139241	784649
503717	985631	994583	993827	998969	994013	999959	999809	757553	631061	617537	680189	912089	519413	532739	691949	576743	594953	527753	920399	150083	44687	20939	20789	227	800897	191	41	5987	1031	6173	5417	14369	496283
579197	996011	997727	988607	991217	992891	999599	702809	880553	644201	926669	695369	623291	955481	930089	818561	749249	707573	32237	651647	28439	2039	147761	21179	3539	30071	449243	401	7109	8783	11393	2273	3989	420803
74051	976211	995909	994949	999359	988343	474983	838247	760301	984329	712133	500321	587711	733847	933839	561047	873317	876797	873641	313661	32771	20051	173651	26849	10091	569	971	710873	11657	641	5051	4091	23789	925949
612023	994559	985679	996407	997037	988367	945899	532451	905621	529349	986813	511019	781217	517481	695243	596243	857579	815279	645419	569201	559913	163193	45491	2111	48593	5801	4073	3461	290183	2963	3593	14321	5441	387977
40169	976439	999023	999437	823787	601751	678383	836267	663239	854171	831653	505073	936869	518327	750119	620813	550241	551093	609887	840611	916187	9203	45131	66449	25583	14621	2609	17	317	747599	563	977	23561	959831
400067	993887	997259	179321	566681	646253	712067	713267	783269	838547	606449	586571	847817	643439	847247	686051	845309	542603	803813	674957	508841	508799	712331	245963	19079	5099	1091	347	389	1181	473219	2741	6113	599933
528107	994811	790733	521657	991889	637283	623537	673781	968273	601631	953651	829757	622709	762821	946853	834797	826019	739391	763913	941609	4673	139079	332987	104537	60029	15413	7451	3803	4409	1487	2621	293207	5189	471893
480317	214451	855461	987929	725897	593987	580409	907331	542483	716447	539207	670823	605789	713957	677681	692663	759131	512927	665111	775091	968027	689219												

Order	Magic Sum 1	Magic Sum 2
4	2000000	4000012
6	3000000	6000018
8	4000000	8000024
10	5000000	10000030
12	6000000	12000036
14	7000000	14000042
16	8000000	16000048
18	9000000	18000054
20	10000000	20000060
22	11000000	22000066
24	12000000	24000072
26	13000000	26000078
28	14000000	28000084
30	15000000	30000090
32	16000000	32000096
34	17000000	34000102
...
80	40000000	80000240
...
120		120000360

3 Odd Order Concentric Prime Magic Squares

Below are few examples of even order **single-layer prime magic squares** starting with magic square of order 3

3.1 Prime Magic Square of Order 3

3	mgc				3000009
	999613	1004677	995719	3000009	
	996109	1000003	1003897	3000009	
	1004287	995329	1000393	3000009	
	3000009	3000009	3000009	3000009	

It is prime magic square of order 4. All the primes are distinct.

3.2 Prime Magic Square of Order 5

5	mgc					5000015
	1996237	569887	517003	1834969	81919	5000015
	567649	999613	1004677	995719	1432357	5000015
	444043	996109	1000003	1003897	1555963	5000015
	73999	1004287	995329	1000393	1926007	5000015
	1918087	1430119	1483003	165037	3769	5000015
	5000015	5000015	5000015	5000015	5000015	5000015

It contains the prime magic square of order 3 given above. All the primes are distinct.

3.3 Prime Magic Square of Order 7

7	mgc							7000021
	23893	372277	674299	348259	1985239	1738837	1857217	7000021
	428797	1996237	569887	517003	1834969	81919	1571209	7000021
	1873513	567649	999613	1004677	995719	1432357	126493	7000021
	1781407	444043	996109	1000003	1003897	1555963	218599	7000021
	1478689	73999	1004287	995329	1000393	1926007	521317	7000021
	1270933	1918087	1430119	1483003	165037	3769	729073	7000021
	142789	1627729	1325707	1651747	14767	261169	1976113	7000021
	7000021	7000021	7000021	7000021	7000021	7000021	7000021	7000021

It contains the prime magic squares of orders 3 and 5 given above. All the primes are distinct.

3.4 Prime Magic Square of Order 9

9	mgc									9000027
	812167	586129	816037	972319	614527	579907	1225723	1898539	1494679	9000027
	986113	23893	372277	674299	348259	1985239	1738837	1857217	1013893	9000027
	93889	428797	1996237	569887	517003	1834969	81919	1571209	1906117	9000027
	614893	1873513	567649	999613	1004677	995719	1432357	126493	1385113	9000027
	427417	1781407	444043	996109	1000003	1003897	1555963	218599	1572589	9000027
	1834663	1478689	73999	1004287	995329	1000393	1926007	521317	165343	9000027
	1934389	1270933	1918087	1430119	1483003	165037	3769	729073	65617	9000027
	1791169	142789	1627729	1325707	1651747	14767	261169	1976113	208837	9000027
	505327	1413877	1183969	1027687	1385479	1420099	774283	101467	1187839	9000027
	9000027	9000027	9000027	9000027	9000027	9000027	9000027	9000027	9000027	9000027

It contains the prime magic squares of orders 3, 5 and 7 given above. All the primes are distinct.

3.5 Prime Magic Square of Order 11

11	mgc											11000033
	721843	501463	310789	4219	860323	906679	603283	1992637	1998943	1934887	1164967	11000033
	754903	812167	586129	816037	972319	614527	579907	1225723	1898539	1494679	1245103	11000033
	707467	986113	23893	372277	674299	348259	1985239	1738837	1857217	1013893	1292539	11000033
	571069	93889	428797	1996237	569887	517003	1834969	81919	1571209	1906117	1428937	11000033
	410953	614893	1873513	567649	999613	1004677	995719	1432357	126493	1385113	1589053	11000033
	357913	427417	1781407	444043	996109	1000003	1003897	1555963	218599	1572589	1642093	11000033
	1677037	1834663	1478689	73999	1004287	995329	1000393	1926007	521317	165343	322969	11000033
	1126537	1934389	1270933	1918087	1430119	1483003	165037	3769	729073	65617	873469	11000033
	1927963	1791169	142789	1627729	1325707	1651747	14767	261169	1976113	208837	72043	11000033
	1909309	505327	1413877	1183969	1027687	1385479	1420099	774283	101467	1187839	90697	11000033
	835039	1498543	1689217	1995787	1139683	1093327	1396723	7369	1063	65119	1278163	11000033
11000033	11000033	11000033	11000033	11000033	11000033	11000033	11000033	11000033	11000033	11000033	11000033	11000033

It contains the prime magic squares of orders 3, 5, 7 and 9 given above. All the primes are distinct.

3.6 Prime Magic Square of Order 13

13	mgc												13000039	
	2953	63607	611587	519433	734887	327343	769807	215983	1890103	1978993	1997467	1971127	1916749	13000039
	230143	721843	501463	310789	4219	860323	906679	603283	1992637	1998943	1934887	1164967	1769863	13000039
	536059	754903	812167	586129	816037	972319	614527	579907	1225723	1898539	1494679	1245103	1463947	13000039
	76873	707467	986113	23893	372277	674299	348259	1985239	1738837	1857217	1013893	1292539	1923133	13000039
	418357	571069	93889	428797	1996237	569887	517003	1834969	81919	1571209	1906117	1428937	1581649	13000039
	429277	410953	614893	1873513	567649	999613	1004677	995719	1432357	126493	1385113	1589053	1570729	13000039
	1968829	357913	427417	1781407	444043	996109	1000003	1003897	1555963	218599	1572589	1642093	31177	13000039
	1864399	1677037	1834663	1478689	73999	1004287	995329	1000393	1926007	521317	165343	322969	135607	13000039
	1445929	1126537	1934389	1270933	1918087	1430119	1483003	165037	3769	729073	65617	873469	554077	13000039
	1969153	1927963	1791169	142789	1627729	1325707	1651747	14767	261169	1976113	208837	72043	30853	13000039
	1999567	1909309	505327	1413877	1183969	1027687	1385479	1420099	774283	101467	1187839	90697	439	13000039
	1975243	835039	1498543	1689217	1995787	1139683	1093327	1396723	7369	1063	65119	1278163	24763	13000039
	83257	1936399	1388419	1480573	1265119	1672663	1230199	1784023	109903	21013	2539	28879	1997053	13000039
13000039	13000039	13000039	13000039	13000039	13000039	13000039	13000039	13000039	13000039	13000039	13000039	13000039	13000039	13000039

It contains the prime magic squares of orders 3, 5, 7, 9 and 11 given above. All the primes are distinct.

3.7 Prime Magic Square of Order 15

15	mgc														15000045	
	1859323	208213	509653	164413	830419	1627	272719	111409	1953517	1640077	1421689	1997503	1998679	1999867	30937	15000045
	746659	2953	63607	611587	519433	734887	327343	769807	215983	1890103	1978993	1997467	1971127	1916749	1253347	15000045
	556849	230143	721843	501463	310789	4219	860323	906679	603283	1992637	1998943	1934887	1164967	1769863	1443157	15000045
	598789	536059	754903	812167	586129	816037	972319	614527	579907	1225723	1898539	1494679	1245103	1463947	1401217	15000045
	487897	76873	707467	986113	23893	372277	674299	348259	1985239	1738837	1857217	1013893	1292539	1923133	1512109	15000045
	810427	418357	571069	93889	428797	1996237	569887	517003	1834969	81919	1571209	1906117	1428937	1581649	1189579	15000045
	891559	429277	410953	614893	1873513	567649	999613	1004677	995719	1432357	126493	1385113	1589053	1570729	1108447	15000045
	784219	1968829	357913	427417	1781407	444043	996109	1000003	1003897	1555963	218599	1572589	1642093	31177	1215787	15000045
	756199	1864399	1677037	1834663	1478689	73999	1004287	995329	1000393	1926007	521317	165343	322969	135607	1243807	15000045
	714739	1445929	1126537	1934389	1270933	1918087	1430119	1483003	165037	3769	729073	65617	873469	554077	1285267	15000045
	724729	1969153	1927963	1791169	142789	1627729	1325707	1651747	14767	261169	1976113	208837	72043	30853	1275277	15000045
	125113	1999567	1909309	505327	1413877	1183969	1027687	1385479	1420099	774283	101467	1187839	90697	439	1874893	15000045
	1985587	1975243	835039	1498543	1689217	1995787	1139683	1093327	1396723	7369	1063	65119	1278163	24763	14419	15000045
	1988887	83257	1936399	1388419	1480573	1265119	1672663	1230199	1784023	109903	21013	2539	28879	1997053	11119	15000045
	1969069	1791793	1490353	1835593	1169587	1998379	1727287	1888597	46489	359929	578317	2503	1327	139	140683	15000045
	15000045	15000045	15000045	15000045	15000045	15000045	15000045	15000045	15000045	15000045	15000045	15000045	15000045	15000045	15000045	15000045

It contains the prime magic squares of orders 3, 5, 7, 9, 11 and 13 given above. All the primes are distinct.

3.8 Prime Magic Square of Order 17

17	mgc																17000051	
	721207	584359	356509	920677	774853	423127	86287	516883	331693	131749	1795327	1889527	1966663	1912213	1998019	1998349	592609	17000051
	868867	1859323	208213	509653	164413	830419	1627	272719	111409	1953517	1640077	1421689	1997503	1998679	1999867	30937	1131139	17000051
	726589	746659	2953	63607	611587	519433	734887	327343	769807	215983	1890103	1978993	1997467	1971127	1916749	1253347	1273417	17000051
	734653	556849	230143	721843	501463	310789	4219	860323	906679	603283	1992637	1998943	1934887	1164967	1769863	1443157	1265353	17000051
	556537	598789	536059	754903	812167	586129	816037	972319	614527	579907	1225723	1898539	1494679	1245103	1463947	1401217	1443469	17000051
	20773	487897	76873	707467	986113	23893	372277	674299	348259	1985239	1738837	1857217	1013893	1292539	1923133	1512109	1979233	17000051
	330607	810427	418357	571069	93889	428797	1996237	569887	517003	1834969	81919	1571209	1906117	1428937	1581649	1189579	1669399	17000051
	75703	891559	429277	410953	614893	1873513	567649	999613	1004677	995719	1432357	126493	1385113	1589053	1570729	1108447	1924303	17000051
	64927	784219	1968829	357913	427417	1781407	444043	996109	1000003	1003897	1555963	218599	1572589	1642093	31177	1215787	1935079	17000051
	883783	756199	1864399	1677037	1834663	1478689	73999	1004287	995329	1000393	1926007	521317	165343	322969	135607	1243807	1116223	17000051
	888109	714739	1445929	1126537	1934389	1270933	1918087	1430119	1483003	165037	3769	729073	65617	873469	554077	1285267	1111897	17000051
	1803973	724729	1969153	1927963	1791169	142789	1627729	1325707	1651747	14767	261169	1976113	208837	72043	30853	1275277	196033	17000051
	1943437	125113	1999567	1909309	505327	1413877	1183969	1027687	1385479	1420099	774283	101467	1187839	90697	439	1874893	56569	17000051
	1993759	1985587	1975243	835039	1498543	1689217	1995787	1139683	1093327	1396723	7369	1063	65119	1278163	24763	14419	6247	17000051
	1997293	1988887	83257	1936399	1388419	1480573	1265119	1672663	1230199	1784023	109903	21013	2539	28879	1997053	11119	2713	17000051
	1982437	1969069	1791793	1490353	1835593	1169587	1998379	1727287	1888597	46489	359929	578317	2503	1327	139	140683	17569	17000051
	1407397	1415647	1643497	1079329	1225153	1576879	1913719	1483123	1668313	1868257	204679	110479	33343	87793	1987	1657	1278799	17000051
	17000051	17000051	17000051	17000051	17000051	17000051	17000051	17000051	17000051	17000051	17000051	17000051	17000051	17000051	17000051	17000051	17000051	17000051

It contains the prime magic squares of orders 3, 5, 7, 9, 11, 13 and 15 given above. All the primes are distinct.

3.9 Prime Magic Square of Order 19

19	mgc																		19000057		
	255349	811729	66883	441523	576553	286513	869203	994579	848227	154873	997933	991777	902137	1684489	1749229	1975627	1999273	1995913	1398247	19000057	
	889489	721207	584359	356509	920677	774853	423127	86287	516883	331693	131749	1795327	1889527	1966663	1912213	1998019	1998349	592609	1110517	19000057	
	259783	868867	1859323	208213	509653	164413	830419	1627	272719	111409	1953517	1640077	1421689	1997503	1998679	1999867	30937	1131139	1740223	19000057	
	195457	726589	746659	2953	63607	611587	519433	734887	327343	769807	215983	1890103	1978993	1997467	1971127	1916749	1253347	1273417	1804549	19000057	
	638263	734653	556849	230143	721843	501463	310789	4219	860323	906679	603283	1992637	1998943	1934887	1164967	1769863	1443157	1265353	1361743	19000057	
	453949	556537	598789	536059	754903	812167	586129	816037	972319	614527	579907	1225723	1898539	1494679	1245103	1463947	1401217	1443469	1546057	19000057	
	714487	20773	487897	76873	707467	986113	23893	372277	674299	348259	1985239	1738837	1857217	1013893	1292539	1923133	1512109	1979233	1285519	19000057	
	321367	330607	810427	418357	571069	93889	428797	1996237	569887	517003	1834969	81919	1571209	1906117	1428937	1581649	1189579	1669399	1678639	19000057	
	115663	75703	891559	429277	410953	614893	1873513	567649	999613	1004677	995719	1432357	126493	1385113	1589053	1570729	1108447	1924303	1884343	19000057	
	158449	64927	784219	1968829	357913	427417	1781407	444043	996109	1000003	1003897	1555963	218599	1572589	1642093	31177	1215787	1935079	1841557	19000057	
	882529	883783	756199	1864399	1677037	1834663	1478689	73999	1004287	995329	1000393	1926007	521317	165343	322969	135607	1243807	1116223	1117477	19000057	
	1798183	888109	714739	1445929	1126537	1934389	1270933	1918087	1430119	1483003	165037	3769	729073	65617	873469	554077	1285267	1111897	201823	19000057	
	1805887	1803973	724729	1969153	1927963	1791169	142789	1627729	1325707	1651747	14767	261169	1976113	208837	72043	30853	1275277	196033	194119	19000057	
	1945597	1943437	125113	1999567	1909309	505327	1413877	1183969	1027687	1385479	1420099	774283	101467	1187839	90697	439	1874893	56569	54409	19000057	
	1994227	1993759	1985587	1975243	835039	1498543	1689217	1995787	1139683	1093327	1396723	7369	1063	65119	1278163	24763	14419	6247	5779	19000057	
	1973143	1997293	1988887	83257	1936399	1388419	1480573	1265119	1672663	1230199	1784023	109903	21013	2539	28879	1997053	11119	2713	26863	19000057	
	1999969	1982437	1969069	1791793	1490353	1835593	1169587	1998379	1727287	1888597	46489	359929	578317	2503	1327	139	140683	17569	37	19000057	
	1996507	1407397	1415647	1643497	1079329	1225153	1576879	1913719	1483123	1668313	1868257	204679	110479	33343	87793	1987	1657	1278799	3499	19000057	
	601759	1188277	1933123	1558483	1423453	1713493	1130803	1005427	1151779	1845133	1002073	1008229	1097869	315517	250777	24379	733	4093	1744657	19000057	
	19000057	19000057	19000057	19000057	19000057	19000057	19000057	19000057	19000057	19000057	19000057	19000057	19000057	19000057	19000057	19000057	19000057	19000057	19000057	19000057	19000057

It contains the prime magic squares of orders 3, 5, 7, 9, 11, 13, 15 and 17 given above. All the primes are distinct.

3.10 Prime Magic Square of Order 21

21	mgc																				21000063
1373473	611953	526087	568207	942013	411127	203947	643243	550489	215617	218437	156823	898753	1674559	1717567	1831447	1978507	1993039	1979683	1988263	516829	21000063
69067	255349	811729	66883	441523	576553	286513	869203	994579	848227	154873	997933	991777	902137	1684489	1749229	1975627	1999273	1995913	1398247	1930939	21000063
308587	889489	721207	584359	356509	920677	774853	423127	86287	516883	331693	131749	1795327	1889527	1966663	1912213	1998019	1998349	592609	1110517	1691419	21000063
265813	259783	868867	1859323	208213	509653	164413	830419	1627	272719	111409	1953517	1640077	1421689	1997503	1998679	1999867	30937	1131139	1740223	1734193	21000063
511963	195457	726589	746659	2953	63607	611587	519433	734887	327343	769807	215983	1890103	1978993	1997467	1971127	1916749	1253347	1273417	1804549	1488043	21000063
385249	638263	734653	556849	230143	721843	501463	310789	4219	860323	906679	603283	1992637	1998943	1934887	1164967	1769863	1443157	1265353	1361743	1614757	21000063
325219	453949	556537	598789	536059	754903	812167	586129	816037	972319	614527	579907	1225723	1898539	1494679	1245103	1463947	1401217	1443469	1546057	1674787	21000063
363757	714487	20773	487897	76873	707467	986113	23893	372277	674299	348259	1985239	1738837	1857217	1013893	1292539	1923133	1512109	1979233	1285519	1636249	21000063
293467	321367	330607	810427	418357	571069	93889	428797	1996237	569887	517003	1834969	81919	1571209	1906117	1428937	1581649	1189579	1669399	1678639	1706539	21000063
399613	115663	75703	891559	429277	410953	614893	1873513	567649	999613	1004677	995719	1432357	126493	1385113	1589053	1570729	1108447	1924303	1884343	1600393	21000063
593059	158449	64927	784219	1968829	357913	427417	1781407	444043	996109	1000003	1003897	1555963	218599	1572589	1642093	31177	1215787	1935079	1841557	1406947	21000063
580033	882529	883783	756199	1864399	1677037	1834663	1478689	73999	1004287	995329	1000393	1926007	521317	165343	322969	135607	1243807	1116223	1117477	1419973	21000063
610843	1798183	888109	714739	1445929	1126537	1934389	1270933	1918087	1430119	1483003	165037	3769	729073	65617	873469	554077	1285267	1111897	201823	1389163	21000063
1914103	1805887	1803973	724729	1969153	1927963	1791169	142789	1627729	1325707	1651747	14767	261169	1976113	208837	72043	30853	1275277	196033	194119	85903	21000063
1597873	1945597	1943437	125113	1999567	1909309	505327	1413877	1183969	1027687	1385479	1420099	774283	101467	1187839	90697	439	1874893	56569	54409	402133	21000063
1989049	1994227	1993759	1985587	1975243	835039	1498543	1689217	1995787	1139683	1093327	1396723	7369	1063	65119	1278163	24763	14419	6247	5779	10957	21000063
1980409	1973143	1997293	1988887	83257	1936399	1388419	1480573	1265119	1672663	1230199	1784023	109903	21013	2539	28879	1997053	11119	2713	26863	19597	21000063
1988689	1999969	1982437	1969069	1791793	1490353	1835593	1169587	1998379	1727287	1888597	46489	359929	578317	2503	1327	139	140683	17569	37	11317	21000063
1997173	1996507	1407397	1415647	1643497	1079329	1225153	1576879	1913719	1483123	1668313	1868257	204679	110479	33343	87793	1987	1657	1278799	3499	2833	21000063
1969447	601759	1188277	1933123	1558483	1423453	1713493	1130803	1005427	1151779	1845133	1002073	1008229	1097869	315517	250777	24379	733	4093	1744657	30559	21000063
1483177	1388053	1473919	1431799	1057993	1588879	1796059	1356763	1449517	1784389	1781569	1843183	1101253	325447	282439	168559	21499	6967	20323	11743	626533	21000063
21000063	21000063	21000063	21000063	21000063	21000063	21000063	21000063	21000063	21000063	21000063	21000063	21000063	21000063	21000063	21000063	21000063	21000063	21000063	21000063	21000063	21000063

It contains the prime magic squares of orders 3, 5, 7, 9, 11, 13, 15, 17 and 19 given above. All the primes are distinct.

3.11 Prime Magic Square of Order 23

23	mgc																					23000069	
1865329	479023	65629	547453	373669	768409	556609	791317	764587	878167	455599	614179	154423	522787	1870717	1828243	1907527	1572679	1895263	1627237	1777717	1675579	7927	23000069
689869	1373473	611953	526087	568207	942013	411127	203947	643243	550489	215617	218437	156823	898753	1674559	1717567	1831447	1978507	1993039	1979683	1988263	516829	1310137	23000069
867079	69067	255349	811729	66883	441523	576553	286513	869203	994579	848227	154873	997933	991777	902137	1684489	1749229	1975627	1999273	1995913	1398247	1930939	1132927	23000069
970069	308587	889489	721207	584359	356509	920677	774853	423127	86287	516883	331693	131749	1795327	1889527	1966663	1912213	1998019	1998349	592609	1110517	1691419	1029937	23000069
664549	265813	259783	868867	1859323	208213	509653	164413	830419	1627	272719	111409	1953517	1640077	1421689	1997503	1998679	1999867	30937	1131139	1740223	1734193	1335457	23000069
556279	511963	195457	726589	746659	2953	63607	611587	519433	734887	327343	769807	215983	1890103	1978993	1997467	1971127	1916749	1253347	1273417	1804549	1488043	1443727	23000069
924727	385249	638263	734653	556849	230143	721843	501463	310789	4219	860323	906679	603283	1992637	1998943	1934887	1164967	1769863	1443157	1265353	1361743	1614757	1075279	23000069
342379	325219	453949	556537	598789	536059	754903	812167	586129	816037	972319	614527	579907	1225723	1898539	1494679	1245103	1463947	1401217	1443469	1546057	1674787	1657627	23000069
329143	363757	714487	20773	487897	76873	707467	986113	23893	372277	674299	348259	1985239	1738837	1857217	1013893	1292539	1923133	1512109	1979233	1285519	1636249	1670863	23000069
80713	293467	321367	330607	810427	418357	571069	93889	428797	1996237	569887	517003	1834969	81919	1571209	1906117	1428937	1581649	1189579	1669399	1678639	1706539	1919293	23000069
419803	399613	115663	75703	891559	429277	410953	614893	1873513	567649	999613	1004677	995719	1432357	126493	1385113	1589053	1570729	1108447	1924303	1884343	1600393	1580203	23000069
561559	593059	158449	64927	784219	1968829	357913	427417	1781407	444043	996109	1000003	1003897	1555963	218599	1572589	1642093	31177	1215787	1935079	1841557	1406947	1438447	23000069
365689	580033	882529	883783	756199	1864399	1677037	1834663	1478689	73999	1004287	995329	1000393	1926007	521317	165343	322969	135607	1243807	1116223	1117477	1419973	1634317	23000069
420367	610843	1798183	888109	714739	1445929	1126537	1934389	1270933	1918087	1430119	1483003	165037	3769	729073	65617	873469	554077	1285267	1111897	201823	1389163	1579639	23000069
518059	1914103	1805887	1803973	724729	1969153	1927963	1791169	142789	1627729	1325707	1651747	14767	261169	1976113	208837	72043	30853	1275277	196033	194119	85903	1481947	23000069
112927	1597873	1945597	1943437	125113	1999567	1909309	505327	1413877	1183969	1027687	1385479	1420099	774283	101467	1187839	90697	439	1874893	56569	54409	402133	1887079	23000069
1879723	1989049	1994227	1993759	1985587	1975243	835039	1498543	1689217	1995787	1139683	1093327	1396723	7369	1063	65119	1278163	24763	14419	6247	5779	10957	120283	23000069
1632637	1980409	1973143	1997293	1988887	83257	1936399	1388419	1480573	1265119	1672663	1230199	1784023	109903	21013	2539	28879	1997053	11119	2713	26863	19597	367369	23000069
1921363	1988689	1999969	1982437	1969069	1791793	1490353	1835593	1169587	1998379	1727287	1888597	46489	359929	578317	2503	1327	139	140683	17569	37	11317	78643	23000069
1945873	1997173	1996507	1407397	1415647	1643497	1079329	1225153	1576879	1913719	1483123	1668313	1868257	204679	110479	33343	87793	1987	1657	1278799	3499	2833	54133	23000069
1993477	1969447	601759	1188277	1933123	1558483	1423453	1713493	1130803	1005427	1151779	1845133	1002073	1008229	1097869	315517	250777	24379	733	4093	1744657	30559	6529	23000069
1946377	1483177	1388053	1473919	1431799	1057993	1588879	1796059	1356763	1449517	1784389	1781569	1843183	1101253	325447	282439	168559	21499	6967	20323	11743	626533	53629	23000069
1992079	1520983	1934377	1452553	1626337	1231597	1443397	1208689	1235419	1121839	1544407	1385827	1845583	1477219	129289	171763	92479	427327	104743	372769	222289	324427	134677	23000069
23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069

It contains the prime magic squares of orders 3, 5, 7, 9, 11, 13, 15, 17, 19 and 21 given above. All the primes are distinct.

3.12 Prime Magic Square of Order 25

25	mgc																									25000075	
	17419	434683	552793	981049	80329	699367	706267	602947	459223	941023	552379	723103	651943	395449	581767	1954717	1898077	468109	1844923	1995583	1998397	1995073	1997119	1996279	472057	25000075	
	486589	1865329	479023	65629	547453	373669	768409	556609	791317	764587	878167	455599	614179	154423	522787	1870717	1828243	1907527	1572679	1895263	1627237	1777717	1675579	7927	1513417	25000075	
	312349	689869	1373473	611953	526087	568207	942013	411127	203947	643243	550489	215617	218437	156823	898753	1674559	1717567	1831447	1978507	1993039	1979683	1988263	516829	1310137	1687657	25000075	
	997897	867079	69067	255349	811729	66883	441523	576553	286513	869203	994579	848227	154873	997933	991777	902137	1684489	1749229	1975627	1999273	1995913	1398247	1930939	1132927	1002109	25000075	
	36007	970069	308587	889489	721207	584359	356509	920677	774853	423127	86287	516883	331693	131749	1795327	1889527	1966663	1912213	1998019	1998349	592609	1110517	1691419	1029937	1963999	25000075	
	19759	664549	265813	259783	868867	1859323	208213	509653	164413	830419	1627	272719	111409	1953517	1640077	1421689	1997503	1998679	1999867	30937	1131139	1740223	1734193	1335457	1980247	25000075	
	510613	556279	511963	195457	726589	746659	2953	63607	611587	519433	734887	327343	769807	215983	1890103	1978993	1997467	1971127	1916749	1253347	1273417	1804549	1488043	1443727	1489393	25000075	
	105667	924727	385249	638263	734653	556849	230143	721843	501463	310789	4219	860323	906679	603283	1992637	1998943	1934887	1164967	1769863	1443157	1265353	1361743	1614757	1075279	1894339	25000075	
	791797	342379	325219	453949	556537	598789	536059	754903	812167	586129	816037	972319	614527	579907	1225723	1898539	1494679	1245103	1463947	1401217	1443469	1546057	1674787	1657627	1208209	25000075	
	209263	329143	363757	714487	20773	487897	76873	707467	986113	23893	372277	674299	348259	1985239	1738837	1857217	1013893	1292539	1923133	1512109	1979233	1285519	1636249	1670863	1790743	25000075	
	33199	80713	293467	321367	330607	810427	418357	571069	93889	428797	1996237	569887	517003	1834969	81919	1571209	1906117	1428937	1581649	1189579	1669399	1678639	1706539	1919293	1966807	25000075	
	278233	419803	399613	115663	75703	891559	429277	410953	614893	1873513	567649	999613	1004677	995719	1432357	126493	1385113	1589053	1570729	1108447	1924303	1884343	1600393	1580203	1721773	25000075	
	13249	561559	593059	158449	64927	784219	1968829	357913	427417	1781407	444043	996109	1000003	1003897	1555963	218599	1572589	1642093	31177	1215787	1935079	1841557	1406947	1438447	1986757	25000075	
	24859	365689	580033	882529	883783	756199	1864399	1677037	1834663	1478689	73999	1004287	995329	1000393	1926007	521317	165343	322969	135607	1243807	1116223	1117477	1419973	1634317	1975147	25000075	
	1770547	420367	610843	1798183	888109	714739	1445929	1126537	1934389	1270933	1918087	1430119	1483003	165037	3769	729073	65617	873469	554077	1285267	1111897	201823	1389163	1579639	229459	25000075	
	1922689	518059	1914103	1805887	1803973	724729	1969153	1927963	1791169	142789	1627729	1325707	1651747	14767	261169	1976113	208837	72043	30853	1275277	196033	194119	85903	1481947	77317	25000075	
	1997539	112927	1597873	1945597	1943437	125113	1999567	1909309	505327	1413877	1183969	1027687	1385479	1420099	774283	101467	1187839	90697	439	1874893	56569	54409	402133	1887079	2467	25000075	
	1991443	1879723	1989049	1994227	1993759	1985587	1975243	835039	1498543	1689217	1995787	1139683	1093327	1396723	7369	1063	65119	1278163	24763	14419	6247	5779	10957	120283	8563	25000075	
	1965637	1632637	1980409	1973143	1997293	1988887	83257	1936399	1388419	1480573	1265119	1672663	1230199	1784023	109903	21013	2539	28879	1997053	11119	2713	26863	19597	367369	34369	25000075	
	1990237	1921363	1988689	1999969	1982437	1969069	1791793	1490353	1835593	1169587	1998379	1727287	1888597	46489	359929	578317	2503	1327	139	140683	17569	37	11317	78643	9769	25000075	
	1999297	1945873	1997173	1996507	1407397	1415647	1643497	1079329	1225153	1576879	1913719	1483123	1668313	1868257	204679	110479	33343	87793	1987	1657	1278799	3499	2833	54133	709	25000075	
	1999549	1993477	1969447	601759	1188277	1933123	1558483	1423453	1713493	1130803	1005427	1151779	1845133	1002073	1008229	1097869	315517	250777	24379	733	4093	1744657	30559	6529	457	25000075	
	1999069	1946377	1483177	1388053	1473919	1431799	1057993	1588879	1796059	1356763	1449517	1784389	1781569	1843183	1101253	325447	282439	168559	21499	6967	20323	11743	626533	53629	937	25000075	
	1999219	1992079	1520983	1934377	1452553	1626337	1231597	1443397	1208689	1235419	1121839	1544407	1385827	1845583	1477219	129289	171763	92479	427327	104743	372769	222289	324427	134677	787	25000075	
	1527949	1565323	1447213	1018957	1919677	1300639	1293739	1397059	1540783	1058983	1447627	1276903	1348063	1604557	1418239	45289	101929	1531897	155083	4423	1609	4933	2887	3727	1982587	25000075	
25000075	25000075	25000075	25000075	25000075	25000075	25000075	25000075	25000075	25000075	25000075	25000075	25000075	25000075	25000075	25000075	25000075	25000075	25000075	25000075	25000075	25000075	25000075	25000075	25000075	25000075	25000075	25000075

It contains the prime magic squares of orders 3, 5, 7, 9, 11, 13, 15, 17, 19, 21 and 23 given above. All the primes are distinct.

3.13 Prime Magic Square of Order 27

27	mgc																									27000081		
197919	298693	914827	16993	760783	237673	930079	479419	613549	485593	179107	549259	142837	300757	786349	817039	477637	1838989	1158799	1936153	1964203	1992517	1998517	1998133	1997617	1998343	147097	27000081	
479299	17419	434683	552793	981049	80329	699367	706267	602947	459223	941023	552379	723103	651943	395449	581767	1954717	1898077	468109	1844923	1995583	1998397	1995073	1997119	1996279	472057	1520707	27000081	
731593	486589	1865329	479023	65629	547453	373669	768409	556609	791317	764587	878167	455599	614179	154423	522787	1870717	1828243	1907527	1572679	1895263	1627237	1777717	1675579	7927	1513417	1268413	27000081	
990013	312349	689869	1373473	611953	526087	568207	942013	411127	203947	643243	550489	215617	218437	156823	898753	1674559	1717567	1831447	1978507	1993039	1979683	1988263	516829	1310137	1687657	1009993	27000081	
321403	997897	867079	69067	255349	811729	66883	441523	576553	286513	869203	994579	848227	154873	997933	991777	902137	1684489	1749229	1975627	1999273	1995913	1398247	1930939	1132927	1002109	1678603	27000081	
945289	36007	970069	308587	889489	721207	584359	356509	920677	774853	423127	86287	516883	331693	131749	1795327	1889527	1966663	1912213	1998019	1998349	592609	1110517	1691419	1029937	1963999	1054717	27000081	
775777	19759	664549	265813	259783	868867	1859323	208213	509653	164413	830419	1627	272719	111409	1953517	1640077	1421689	1997503	1998679	1999867	30937	1131139	1740223	1734193	1335457	1980247	1224229	27000081	
105613	510613	556279	511963	195457	726589	746659	2953	63607	611587	519433	734887	327343	769807	215983	1890103	1978993	1997467	1971127	1916749	1253347	1273417	1804549	1488043	1443727	1489393	1894393	27000081	
696373	105667	924727	385249	638263	734653	556849	230143	721843	501463	310789	4219	860323	906679	603283	1992637	1998943	1934887	1164967	1769863	1443157	1265353	1361743	1614757	1075279	1894339	1303633	27000081	
273067	791797	342379	325219	453949	556537	598789	536059	754903	812167	586129	816037	972319	614527	579907	1225723	1898539	1494679	1245103	1463947	1401217	1443469	1546057	1674787	1657627	1208209	1726939	27000081	
26317	209263	329143	363757	714487	20773	487897	76873	707467	986113	23893	372277	674299	348259	1985239	1738837	1857217	1013893	1292539	1923133	1512109	1979233	1285519	1636249	1670863	1790743	1973689	27000081	
349579	33199	80713	293467	321367	330607	810427	418357	571069	93889	428797	1996237	569887	517003	1834969	81919	1571209	1906117	1428937	1581649	1189579	1669399	1678639	1706539	1919293	1966807	1650427	27000081	
660799	278233	419803	399613	115663	75703	891559	429277	410953	614893	1873513	567649	999613	1004677	995719	1432357	126493	1385113	1589053	1570729	1108447	1924303	1884343	1600393	1580203	1721773	1339207	27000081	
117259	13249	561559	593059	158449	64927	784219	1968829	357913	427417	1781407	444043	996109	1000003	1003897	1555963	218599	1572589	1642093	31177	1215787	1935079	1841557	1406947	1438447	1986757	1882747	27000081	
856519	24859	365689	580033	882529	883783	756199	1864399	1677037	1834663	1478689	73999	1004287	995329	1000393	1926007	521317	165343	322969	135607	1243807	1116223	1117477	1419973	1634317	1975147	1143487	27000081	
135349	1770547	420367	610843	1798183	888109	714739	1445929	1126537	1934389	1270933	1918087	1430119	1483003	165037	3769	729073	65617	873469	554077	1111897	201823	1389163	1579639	229459	1864657	27000081		
945739	1922689	518059	1914103	1805887	1803973	724729	1969153	1927963	1791169	142789	1627729	1325707	1651747	14767	261169	1976113	208837	72043	30853	1275277	196033	194119	85903	1481947	77317	1054267	27000081	
598999	1997539	112927	1597873	1945597	1943437	125113	1999567	1909309	505327	1413877	1183969	1027687	1385479	1420099	774283	101467	1187839	90697	439	1874893	56569	54409	402133	1887079	2467	1401007	27000081	
1912423	1991443	1879723	1989049	1994227	1993759	1985587	1975243	835039	1498543	1689217	1995787	1139683	1093327	1396723	7369	1063	65119	1278163	24763	14419	6247	5779	10957	120283	8563	87583	27000081	
291043	1965637	1632637	1980409	1973143	1997293	1988887	83257	1936399	1388419	1480573	1265119	1672663	1230199	1784023	109903	21013	2539	28879	1997053	11119	2713	26863	19597	367369	34369	1708963	27000081	
1991989	1990237	1921363	1988689	1999969	1982437	1969069	1791793	1490353	1835593	1169587	1998379	1727287	1888597	46489	359929	578317	2503	1327	139	140683	17569	37	11317	78643	9769	8017	27000081	
1981513	1999297	1945873	1997173	1996507	1407397	1415647	1643497	1079329	1225153	1576879	1913719	1483123	1668313	1868257	204679	110479	33343	87793	1987	1657	1278799	3499	2833	54133	709	18493	27000081	
1998223	1999549	1993477	1969447	601759	1188277	1933123	1558483	1423453	1713493	1130803	1005427	1151779	1845133	1002073	1008229	1097869	315517	250777	24379	733	4093	1744657	30559	6529	457	1783	27000081	
1990033	1999069	1946377	1483177	1388053	1473919	1431799	1057993	1588879	1796059	1356763	1449517	1784389	1781569	1843183	1101253	325447	282439	168559	21499	6967	20323	11743	626533	53629	937	9973	27000081	
1999363	1999219	1992079	1520983	1934377	1452553	1626337	1231597	1443397	1208689	1235419	1121839	1544407	1385827	1845583	1477219	129289	171763	92479	427327	104743	372769	222289	324427	134677	787	643	27000081	
1994479	1527949	1565323	1447213	1018957	1919677	1300639	1293739	1397059	1540783	1058983	1447627	1276903	1348063	1604557	1418239	45289	101929	1531897	155083	4423	1609	4933	2887	3727	1982587	5527	27000081	
1852909	1701313	1085179	1983013	1239223	1762333	1069927	1520587	1386457	1514413	1820899	1450747	1857169	1699249	1213657	1182967	1522369	161017	841207	63853	35803	7489	1489	1873	2389	1663	20887	27000081	
27000081	27000081	27000081	27000081	27000081	27000081	27000081	27000081	27000081	27000081	27000081	27000081	27000081	27000081	27000081	27000081	27000081	27000081	27000081	27000081	27000081	27000081	27000081	27000081	27000081	27000081	27000081	27000081	27000081

It contains the prime magic squares of orders 3, 5, 7, 9, 11, 13, 15, 17, 19, 21, 23 and 25 given above. All the primes are distinct.

3.14 Prime Magic Square of Order 29

29	mgc																												29000087	
1891297	184447	340129	378283	286633	358417	635989	301759	978883	772669	333349	145303	621997	821383	464419	866197	659059	319687	473953	1904467	1933549	1919773	1950889	1990123	1993933	1998457	1998793	1999177	477073	29000087	
155719	1979119	298693	914827	16993	760783	237673	930079	479419	613549	485593	179107	549259	142837	300757	786349	817039	477637	1838989	1158799	1936153	1964203	1992517	1998517	1998133	1997617	1998343	147097	1844287	29000087	
541987	479299	17419	434683	552793	981049	80329	699367	706267	602947	459223	941023	552379	723103	651943	395449	581767	1954717	1898077	468109	1844923	1995583	1998397	1995073	1997119	1996279	472057	1520707	1458019	29000087	
86959	731593	486589	1865329	479023	65629	547453	373669	768409	556609	791317	764587	878167	455599	614179	154423	522787	1870717	1828243	1907527	1572679	1895263	1627237	1777717	1675579	7927	1513417	1268413	1913047	29000087	
197203	990013	312349	689869	1373473	611953	526087	568207	942013	411127	203947	643243	550489	215617	218437	156823	898753	1674559	1717567	1831447	1978507	1993039	1979683	1988263	516829	1310137	1687657	1009993	1802803	29000087	
34123	321403	997897	867079	69067	255349	811729	66883	441523	576553	286513	869203	994579	848227	154873	997933	991777	902137	1684489	1749229	1975627	1999273	1995913	1398247	1930939	1132927	1002109	1678603	1965883	29000087	
766387	945289	36007	970069	308587	889489	721207	584359	356509	920677	774853	423127	86287	516883	331693	131749	1795327	1889527	1966663	1912213	1998019	1998349	592609	1110517	1691419	1029937	1963999	1054717	1233619	29000087	
872479	775777	19759	664549	265813	259783	868867	1859323	208213	509653	164413	830419	1627	272719	111409	1953517	1640077	1421689	1997503	1998679	1999867	30937	1131139	1740223	1734193	1335457	1980247	1224229	1127527	29000087	
658219	105613	510613	556279	511963	195457	726589	746659	2953	63607	611587	519433	734887	327343	769807	215983	1890103	1978993	1997467	1971127	1916749	1253347	1273417	1804549	1488043	1443727	1489393	1894393	1341787	29000087	
649879	696373	105667	924727	385249	638263	734653	556849	230143	721843	501463	310789	4219	860323	906679	603283	1992637	1998943	1934887	1164967	1769863	1443157	1265353	1361743	1614757	1075279	1894339	1303633	1350127	29000087	
63703	273067	791797	342379	325219	453949	556537	598789	536059	754903	812167	586129	816037	972319	614527	579907	1225723	1898539	1494679	1245103	1463947	1401217	1443469	1546057	1674787	1657627	1208209	1726939	1936303	29000087	
35569	26317	209263	329143	363757	714487	20773	487897	76873	707467	986113	23893	372277	674299	348259	1985239	1738837	1857217	1013893	1292539	1923133	1512109	1979233	1285519	1636249	1670863	1790743	1973689	1964437	29000087	
750517	349579	33199	80713	293467	321367	330607	810427	418357	571069	93889	428797	1996237	569887	517003	1834969	81919	1571209	1906117	1428937	1581649	1189579	1669399	1678639	1706539	1919293	1966807	1650427	1249489	29000087	
702337	660799	278233	419803	399613	115663	75703	891559	429277	410953	614893	1873513	567649	999613	1004677	995719	1432357	126493	1385113	1589053	1570729	1108447	1924303	1884343	1600393	1580203	1721773	1339207	1297669	29000087	
105037	117259	13249	561559	593059	158449	64927	784219	1968829	357913	427417	1781407	444043	996109	1000003	1003897	1555963	218599	1572589	1642093	31177	1215787	1935079	1841557	1406947	1438447	1986757	1882747	1894969	29000087	
993037	856519	24859	365689	580033	882529	883783	756199	1864399	1677037	1834663	1478689	73999	1004287	995329	1000393	1926007	521317	165343	322969	135607	1243807	1116223	1117477	1419973	1634317	1975147	1143487	1006969	29000087	
843757	135349	1770547	420367	610843	1798183	888109	714739	1445929	1126537	1934389	1270933	1918087	1430119	1483003	165037	3769	729073	65617	873469	554077	1285267	1111897	201823	1389163	1579639	229459	1864657	1156249	29000087	
314233	945739	1922689	518059	1914103	1805887	1803973	724729	1969153	1927963	1791169	142789	1627729	1325707	1651747	14767	261169	1976113	208837	72043	30853	1275277	196033	194119	85903	1481947	77317	1054267	1685773	29000087	
400753	598999	1997539	112927	1597873	1945597	1943437	125113	1999567	1909309	505327	1413877	1183969	1027687	1385479	1420099	774283	101467	1187839	90697	439	1874893	56569	54409	402133	1887079	2467	1401007	1599253	29000087	
1726009	1912423	1991443	1879723	1989049	1994227	1993759	1985587	1975243	835039	1498543	1689217	1995787	1139683	1093327	1396723	7369	1063	65119	1278163	24763	14419	6247	5779	10957	120283	8563	87583	273997	29000087	
1829449	291043	1965637	1632637	1980409	1973143	1997293	1988887	83257	1936399	1388419	1480573	1265119	1672663	1230199	1784023	109903	21013	2539	28879	1997053	11119	2713	26863	19597	367369	34369	1708963	170557	29000087	
1892167	1991989	1990237	1921363	1988689	1999969	1982437	1969069	1791793	1490353	1835593	1169587	1998379	1727287	1888597	46489	359929	578317	2503	1327	139	140683	17569	37	11317	78643	9769	8017	107839	29000087	
1982083	1981513	1999297	1945873	1997173	1996507	1407397	1415647	1643497	1079329	1225153	1576879	1913719	1483123	1668313	1868257	204679	110479	33343	87793	1987	1657	1278799	3499	2833	54133	709	18493	17923	29000087	
1987099	1998223	1999549	1993477	1969447	601759	1188277	1933123	1558483	1423453	1713493	1130803	1005427	1151779	1845133	1002073	1008229	1097869	315517	250777	24379	733	4093	1744657	30559	6529	457	1783	12907	29000087	
1998427	1990033	1999069	1946377	1483177	1388053	1473919	1431799	1057993	1588879	1796059	1356763	1449517	1784389	1781569	1843183	1101253	325447	282439	168559	21499	6967	20323	11743	626533	53629	937	9973	1579	29000087	
1999099	1999363	1999219	1992079	1520983	1934377	1452553	1626337	1231597	1443397	1208689	1235419	1121839	1544407	1385827	1845583	1477219	129289	171763	92479	427327	104743	372769	222289	324427	134677	787	643	907	29000087	
1999633	1994479	1527949	1565323	1447213	1018957	1919677	1300639	1293739	1397059	1540783	1058983	1447627	1276903	1348063	1604557	1418239	45289	101929	1531897	155083	4423	1609	4933	2887	3727	1982587	5527	373	29000087	
1999993	1852909	1701313	1085179	1983013	1239223	1762333	1069927	1520587	1386457	1514413	1820899	1450747	1857169	1699249	1213657	1182967	1522369	161017	841207	63853	35803	7489	1489	1873	2389	1663	20887	13	29000087	
1522933	1815559	1659877	1621723	1713373	1641589	1364017	1698247	1021123	1227337	1666657	1854703	1378009	1178623	1535587	1133809	1340947	1680319	1526053	95539	66457	80233	49117	9883	6073	1549	1213	829	108709	29000087	
29000087	29000087	29000087	29000087	29000087	29000087	29000087	29000087	29000087	29000087	29000087	29000087	29000087	29000087	29000087	29000087	29000087	29000087	29000087	29000087	29000087	29000087	29000087	29000087	29000087	29000087	29000087	29000087	29000087	29000087	29000087

It contains the prime magic squares of orders 3, 5, 7, 9, 11, 13, 15, 17, 19, 21, 23, 25 and 27 given above. All the primes are distinct.

3.15 Prime Magic Square of Order 31

720253	106363	69127	337453	623803	818359	113809	714949	89329	905197	450529	7129	285049	181087	761809	134287	685123	720703	1941307	1951597	1913683	1850509	1690693	1921747	1885459	1934683	1949887	1937953	1992937	1984117	321163
769057	1891297	184447	340129	378283	286633	358417	635989	301759	978883	772669	333349	145303	621997	821383	464419	866197	659059	319687	473953	1904467	1933549	1919773	1950889	1990123	1993933	1998457	1998793	1999177	477073	1230949
925159	155719	1979119	298693	914827	16993	760783	237673	930079	479419	613549	485593	179107	549259	142837	300757	786349	817039	477637	1838989	1158799	1936153	1964203	1992517	1998517	1998133	1997617	1998343	147097	1844287	1074847
729493	541987	479299	17419	434683	552793	981049	80329	699367	706267	602947	459223	941023	552379	723103	651943	395449	581767	1954717	1898077	468109	1844923	1995583	1998397	1995073	1997119	1996279	472057	1520707	1458019	1270513
374989	86959	731593	486589	1865329	479023	65629	547453	373669	768409	556609	791317	764587	878167	455599	614179	154423	522787	1870717	1828243	1907527	1572679	1895263	1627237	1777717	1675579	7927	1513417	1268413	1913047	1625017
61057	197203	990013	312349	689869	1373473	611953	526087	568207	942013	411127	203947	643243	550489	215617	218437	156823	898753	1674559	1717567	1831447	1978507	1993039	1979683	1988263	516829	1310137	1687657	1009993	1802803	1938949
470209	34123	321403	997897	867079	69067	255349	811729	66883	441523	576553	286513	869203	994579	848227	154873	997933	991777	902137	1684489	1749229	1975627	1999273	1995913	1398247	1930939	1132927	1002109	1678603	1965883	1529797
330469	766387	945289	36007	970069	308587	889489	721207	584359	356509	920677	774853	423127	86287	516883	331693	131749	1795327	1889527	1966663	1912213	1998019	1998349	592609	1110517	1691419	1029937	1963999	1054717	1233619	1669537
247999	872479	775777	19759	664549	265813	259783	868867	1859323	208213	509653	164413	830419	1627	272719	111409	1953517	1640077	1421689	1997503	1998679	1999867	30937	1131139	1740223	1734193	1335457	1980247	1224229	1127527	1752007
329503	658219	105613	510613	556279	511963	195457	726589	746659	2953	63607	611587	519433	734887	327343	769807	215983	1890103	1978993	1997467	1971127	1916749	1253347	1273417	1804549	1488043	1443727	1489393	1894393	1341787	1670503
78193	649879	696373	105667	924727	385249	638263	734653	556849	230143	721843	501463	310789	4219	860323	906679	603283	1992637	1998943	1934887	1164967	1769863	1443157	1265353	1361743	1614757	1075279	1894339	1303633	1350127	1921813
191449	63703	273067	791797	342379	325219	453949	556537	598789	536059	754903	812167	586129	816037	972319	614527	579907	1225723	1898539	1494679	1245103	1463947	1401217	1443469	1546057	1674787	1657627	1208209	1726939	1936303	1808557
244687	35569	26317	209263	329143	363757	714487	20773	487897	76873	707467	986113	23893	372277	674299	348259	1985239	1738837	1857217	1013893	1292539	1923133	1512109	1979233	1285519	1636249	1670863	1790743	1973689	1964437	1755319
656959	750517	349579	33199	80713	293467	321367	330607	810427	418357	571069	93889	428797	1996237	569887	517003	1834969	81919	1571209	1906117	1428937	1581649	1189579	1669399	1678639	1706539	1919293	1966807	1650427	1249489	1343047
253243	702337	660799	278233	419803	399613	115663	75703	891559	429277	410953	614893	1873513	567649	999613	1004677	995719	1432357	126493	1385113	1589053	1570729	1108447	1924303	1884343	1600393	1580203	1721773	1339207	1297669	1746763
236077	105037	117259	13249	561559	593059	158449	64927	784219	1968829	357913	427417	1781407	444043	996109	1000003	1003897	1555963	218599	1572589	1642093	31177	1215787	1935079	1841557	1406947	1438447	1986757	1882747	1894969	1763929
82003	993037	856519	24859	365689	580033	882529	883783	756199	1864399	1677037	1834663	1478689	73999	1004287	995329	1000393	1926007	521317	165343	322969	135607	1243807	1116223	1117477	1419973	1634317	1975147	1143487	1006969	1918003
33403	843757	135349	1770547	420367	610843	1798183	888109	714739	1445929	1126537	1934389	1270933	1918087	1430119	1483003	165037	3769	729073	65617	873469	554077	1285267	1111897	201823	1389163	1579639	229459	1864657	1156249	1966603
1889383	314233	945739	1922689	518059	1914103	1805887	1803973	724729	1969153	1927963	1791169	142789	1627729	1325707	1651747	14767	261169	1976113	208837	72043	30853	1275277	196033	194119	85903	1481947	77317	1054267	1685773	110623
1905157	400753	598999	1997539	112927	1597873	1945597	1943437	125113	1999567	1909309	505327	1413877	1183969	1027687	1385479	1420099	774283	101467	1187839	90697	439	1874893	56569	54409	402133	1887079	2467	1401007	1599253	94849
1426003	1726009	1912423	1991443	1879723	1989049	1994227	1993759	1985587	1975243	835039	1498543	1689217	1995787	1139683	1093327	1396723	7369	1063	65119	1278163	24763	14419	6247	5779	10957	120283	8563	87583	273997	574003
1918849	1829449	291043	1965637	1632637	1980409	1973143	1997293	1988887	83257	1936399	1388419	1480573	1265119	1672663	1230199	1784023	109903	21013	2539	28879	1997053	11119	2713	26863	19597	367369	34369	1708963	170557	81157
1591189	1892167	1991989	1990237	1921363	1988689	1999969	1982437	1969069	1791793	1490353	1835593	1169587	1998379	1727287	1888597	46489	359929	578317	2503	1327	139	140683	17569	37	11317	78643	9769	8017	107839	408817
1958773	1982083	1981513	1999297	1945873	1997173	1996507	1407397	1415647	1643497	1079329	1225153	1576879	1913719	1483123	1668313	1868257	204679	110479	33343	87793	1987	1657	1278799	3499	2833	54133	709	18493	17923	41233
1984813	1987099	1998223	1999549	1993477	1969447	601759	1188277	1933123	1558483	1423453	1713493	1130803	1005427	1151779	1845133	1002073	1008229	1097869	315517	250777	24379	733	4093	1744657	30559	6529	457	1783	12907	15193
1992769	1998427	1990033	1999069	1946377	1483177	1388053	1473919	1431799	1057993	1588879	1796059	1356763	1449517	1784389	1781569	1843183	1101253	325447	282439	168559	21499	6967	20323	11743	626533	53629	937	9973	1579	7237
1996459	1999099	1999363	1999219	1992079	1520983	1934377	1452553	1626337	1231597	1443397	1208689	1235419	1121839	1544407	1385827	1845583	1477219	129289	171763	92479	427327	104743	372769	222289	324427	134677	787	643	907	3547
1991617	1999633	1994479	1527949	1565323	1447213	1018957	1919677	1300639	1293739	1397059	1540783	1058983	1447627	1276903	1348063	1604557	1418239	45289	101929	1531897	155083	4423	1609	4933	2887	3727	1982587	5527	373	8389
1979149	1999993	1852909	1701313	1085179	1983013	1239223	1762333	1069927	1520587	1386457	1514413	1820899	1450747	1857169	1699249	1213657	1182967	1522369	161017	841207	63853	35803	7489	1489	1873	2389	1663	20887	13	20857
1952887	1522933	1815559	1659877	1621723	1713373	1641589	1364017	1698247	1021123	1227337	1666657	1854703	1378009	1178623	1535587	1133809	1340947	1680319	1526053	95539	66457	80233	49117	9883	6073	1549	1213	829	108709	47119
1678843	1893643	1930879	1662553	1376203	1181647	1886197	1285057	1910677	1094809	1549477	1992877	1714957	1818919	1238197	1865719	1314883	1279303	58699	48409	86323	149497	309313	78259	114547	65323	50119	62053	7069	15889	1279753

It contains the prime magic squares of orders 3, 5, 7, 9, 11, 13, 15, 17, 19, 21, 23, 25, 27 and 29 given above. All the primes are distinct.

3.16 Prime Magic Square of Order 33

91249	1490059	1287289	1090963	1787587	479533	1713133	471673	265459	1416769	1198033	1257787	1109887	349519	969049	1558819	1671679	483097	725077	1693753	668407	238423	1068877	1281283	365509	1274857	1354267	246937	990163	64489	1394749	970147	1971577
1557763	720253	106363	69127	337453	623803	818359	113809	714949	89329	905197	450529	7129	285049	181087	761809	134287	685123	720703	1941307	1951597	1913683	1850509	1690693	1921747	1885459	1934683	1949887	1937953	1992937	1984117	321163	442243
184369	769057	1891297	184447	340129	378283	286633	358417	635989	301759	978883	772669	333349	145303	621997	821383	464419	866197	659059	319687	473953	1904467	1933549	1919773	1950889	1990123	1993933	1998457	1998793	1999177	477073	1230949	1815637
1269223	925159	155719	1979119	298693	914827	16993	760783	237673	930079	479419	613549	485593	179107	549259	142837	300757	786349	817039	477637	1838989	1158799	1936153	1964203	1992517	1998517	1998133	1997617	1998343	147097	1844287	1074847	730783
468709	729493	541987	479299	17419	434683	552793	981049	80329	699367	706267	602947	459223	941023	552379	723103	651943	395449	581767	1954717	1898077	468109	1844923	1995583	1998397	1995073	1997119	1996279	472057	1520707	1458019	1270513	1531297
1792387	374989	86959	731593	486589	1865329	479023	65629	547453	373669	768409	556609	791317	764587	878167	455599	614179	154423	522787	1870717	1828243	1907527	1572679	1895263	1627237	1777717	1675579	7927	1513417	1268413	1913047	1625017	207619
379459	61057	197203	990013	312349	689869	1373473	611953	526087	568207	942013	411127	203947	643243	550489	215617	218437	156823	898753	1674559	1717567	1831447	1978507	1993039	1979683	1988263	516829	1310137	1687657	1009993	1802803	1938949	1620547
1702249	470209	34123	321403	997897	867079	69067	255349	811729	66883	441523	576553	286513	869203	994579	848227	154873	997933	991777	902137	1684489	1749229	1975627	1999273	1995913	1398247	1930939	1132927	1002109	1678603	1965883	1529797	297757
363157	330469	766387	945289	36007	970069	308587	889489	721207	584359	356509	920677	774853	423127	86287	516883	331693	131749	1795327	1889527	1966663	1912213	1998019	1998349	592609	1110517	1691419	1029937	1963999	1054717	1233619	1669537	1636849
152533	247999	872479	775777	19759	664549	265813	259783	868867	1859323	208213	509653	164413	830419	1627	272719	111409	1953517	1640077	1421689	1997503	1998679	1999867	30937	1131139	1740223	1734193	1335457	1980247	1224229	1127527	1752007	1847473
440893	329503	658219	105613	510613	556279	511963	195457	726589	746659	2953	63607	611587	519433	734887	327343	769807	215983	1890103	1978993	1997467	1971127	1916749	1253347	1273417	1804549	1488043	1443727	1489393	1894393	1341787	1670503	1559113
1770313	78193	649879	696373	105667	924727	385249	638263	734653	556849	230143	721843	501463	310789	4219	860323	906679	603283	1992637	1998943	1934887	1164967	1769863	1443157	1265353	1361743	1614757	1075279	1894339	1303633	1350127	1921813	229693
1697719	191449	63703	273067	791797	342379	325219	453949	556537	598789	536059	754903	812167	586129	816037	972319	614527	579907	1225723	1898539	1494679	1245103	1463947	1401217	1443469	1546057	1674787	1657627	1208209	1726939	1936303	1808557	302287
1784617	244687	35569	26317	209263	329143	363757	714487	20773	487897	76873	707467	986113	23893	372277	674299	348259	1985239	1738837	1857217	1013893	1292539	1923133	1512109	1979233	1285519	1636249	1670863	1790743	1973689	1964437	1755319	215389
114973	656959	750517	349579	33199	80713	293467	321367	330607	810427	418357	571069	93889	428797	1996237	569887	517003	1834969	81919	1571209	1906117	1428937	1581649	1189579	1669399	1678639	1706539	1919293	1966807	1650427	1249489	1343047	1885033
1372867	253243	702337	660799	278233	419803	399613	115663	75703	891559	429277	410953	614893	1873513	567649	999613	1004677	995719	1432357	126493	1385113	1589053	1570729	1108447	1924303	1884343	1600393	1580203	1721773	1339207	1297669	1746763	627139
1948777	236077	105037	117259	13249	561559	593059	158449	64927	784219	1968829	357913	427417	1781407	444043	996109	1000003	1003897	1555963	218599	1572589	1642093	31177	1215787	1935079	1841557	1406947	1438447	1986757	1882747	1894969	1763929	51229
114013	82003	993037	856519	24859	365689	580033	882529	883783	756199	1864399	1677037	1834663	1478689	73999	1004287	995329	1000393	1926007	521317	165343	322969	135607	1243807	1116223	1117477	1419973	1634317	1975147	1143487	1006969	1918003	1885993
1986913	33403	843757	135349	1770547	420367	610843	1798183	888109	714739	1445929	1126537	1934389	1270933	1918087	1430119	1483003	165037	3769	729073	65617	873469	554077	1285267	1111897	201823	1389163	1579639	229459	1864657	1156249	1966603	13093
1994947	1889383	314233	945739	1922689	518059	1914103	1805887	1803973	724729	1969153	1927963	1791169	142789	1627729	1325707	1651747	14767	261169	1976113	208837	72043	30853	1275277	196033	194119	85903	1481947	77317	1054267	1685773	110623	5059
700717	1905157	400753	598999	1997539	112927	1597873	1945597	1943437	125113	1999567	1909309	505327	1413877	1183969	1027687	1385479	1420099	774283	101467	1187839	90697	439	1874893	56569	54409	402133	1887079	2467	1401007	1599253	94849	1299289
1081723	1426003	1726009	1912423	1991443	1879723	1989049	1994227	1993759	1985587	1975243	835039	1498543	1689217	1995787	1139683	1093327	1396723	7369	1063	65119	1278163	24763	14419	6247	5779	10957	120283	8563	87583	273997	574003	918283
803497	1918849	1829449	291043	1965637	1632637	1980409	1973143	1997293	1988887	83257	1936399	1388419	1480573	1265119	1672663	1230199	1784023	109903	21013	2539	28879	1997053	11119	2713	26863	19597	367369	34369	1708963	170557	81157	1196509
882733	1591189	1892167	1991989	1990237	1921363	1988689	1999969	1982437	1969069	1791793	1490353	1835593	1169587	1998379	1727287	1888597	46489	359929	578317	2503	1327	139	140683	17569	37	11317	78643	9769	8017	107839	408817	1117273
1152343	1958773	1982083	1981513	1999297	1945873	1997173	1996507	1407397	1415647	1643497	1079329	1225153	1576879	1913719	1483123	1668313	1868257	204679	110479	33343	87793	1987	1657	1278799	3499	2833	54133	709	18493	17923	41233	847663
1185103	1984813	1987099	1998223	1999549	1993477	1969447	601759	1188277	1933123	1558483	1423453	1713493	1130803	1005427	1151779	1845133	1002073	1008229	1097869	315517	250777	24379	733	4093	1744657	30559	6529	457	1783	12907	15193	814903
1684693	1992769	1998427	1990033	1999069	1946377	1483177	1388053	1473919	1431799	1057993	1588879	1796059	1356763	1449517	1784389	1781569	1843183	1101253	325447	282439	168559	21499	6967	20323	11743	626533	53629	937	9973	1579	7237	315313
1347103	1996459	1999099	1999363	1999219	1992079	1520983	1934377	1452553	1626337	1231597	1443397	1208689	1235419	1121839	1544407	1385827	1845583	1477219	129289	171763	92479	427327	104743	372769	222289	324427	134677	787	643	907	3547	652903
194413	1991617	1999633	1994479	1527949	1565323	1447213	1018957	1919677	1300639	1293739	1397059	1540783	1058983	1447627	1276903	1348063	1604557	1418239	45289	101929	1531897	155083	4423	1609	4933	2887	3727	1982587	5527	373	8389	1805593
582433	1979149	1999993	1852909	1701313	1085179	1983013	1239223	1762333	1069927	1520587	1386457	1514413	1820899	1450747	1857169	1699249	1213657	1182967	1522369	161017	841207	63853	35803	7489	1489	1873	2389	1663	20887	13	20857	1417573
1976803	1952887	1522933	1815559	1659877	1621723	1713373	1641589	1364017	1698247	1021123	1227337	1666657	1854703	1378009	1178623	1535587	1133809	1340947	1680319	1526053	95539	66457	80233	49117	9883	6073	1549	1213	829	108709	47119	23203
192979	1678843	1893643	1930879	1662553	1376203	1181647	1886197	1285057	1910677	1094809	1549477	1992877	1714957	1818919	1238197	1865719	1314883	1279303	58699	48409	86323	149497	309313	78259	114547	65323	50119	62053	7069	15889	1279753	1

Order	Magic Sum 1
3	3000009
5	5000015
7	7000021
9	9000027
11	11000033
13	13000039
15	15000045
17	17000051
19	19000057
21	21000063
23	23000069
25	25000075
27	27000081
29	29000087
31	31000093
33	33000099
...	...
121	121000363

Remark 3. Both the procedures for even or odd orders are based on a prime constant $C := 1000003$. The same procedure is applied over the prime magic squares of order 1220×1220 with equal sum blocks of order 4 [8]. The order 1220 is reached based on 7-levels. If we apply further levels over the concentric prime magic squares, we get higher orders. This shall be dealt elsewhere. The **excel sheets** of this work are also attached.

4 Author’s Contribution to Recreation of Numbers and Magic Squares

- (i) **Inder J. Taneja**, Recreation of Numbers - <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=671>.
- (ii) **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Squares - <https://numbers-magic.com/?cat=3>. Also for the publications on magic squares see the link: <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=668>.

References

- [1] **H.E. Dudeney**, Amusements in Mathematics, The Authors' Club, 1917.
- [2] **H. Harvey**, Prime Numbers Magic Squares <http://recmath.org/MagicSquares/primesqr.htm>
- [3] **C. Riveira**, The Prime Puzzles and Problem Connections, <https://www.primepuzzles.net/>
- [4] **H. White**, Bordered Magic Squares - <http://budshaw.ca/BorderedMagicSquares.html>
- [5] **H. White**, Magic Squares of Prime Numbers, <https://budshaw.ca/PrimeMagicSquares.html>
- [6] **Makarova, Natalia**, Concentric magic squares of primes, <http://primesmagicgames.altervista.org/wp/forums/topic/concentric-magic-squares-of-primes/>. Also refers: <http://www.natalimak1.narod.ru/sqmin1.htm>; <http://www.natalimak1.narod.ru/sqmin2.htm>; <http://www.natalimak1.narod.ru/sqmin3.htm>; <http://www.klassikpoez.narod.ru/glavnaja.htm>.
- **Prime Magic Squares**
- .
- [7] **Inder J. Taneja**, Single-Layer Bordered Even and Odd Orders Primes Magic Squares: Orders 120 and 121, **Zenodo**, May June 16, 2026, pp. 1-36, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20723312>. Web-site links: <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=19224> and <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=19258>.
- [8] **Inder J. Taneja**, Higher Order Block-Structured Prime Magic Squares: Order 1220 Multiples of 4, **Zenodo**, , June 16, 2026, pp. 1-27, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20723328>. Web-site link: <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=19291>.
- [9] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Structured Prime Magic Squares: Orders 6 to 14, **Zenodo**, June 16, 2026, pp. 1-41, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20723272> Web-site link: <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=19319>.
- [10] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Structured Prime Magic Squares: Orders 15 to 23, **Zenodo**, June 16, 2026, pp. 1-76, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20723291>. Web-site link: <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=19410>.
- [11] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Structured Prime Magic Squares: Orders 24 to 31, In Preparation.

[12] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Structured Prime Magic Squares: Orders 32 to 38, In Preparation.

[13] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Structured Prime Magic Squares: Orders 39 to 45, In Preparation.

[14] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Structured Prime Magic Squares: Orders 46 to 51, In Preparation.

• Bordered Magic Squares

[15] **Inder J. Taneja**, Nested Magic Squares With Perfect Square Sums, Pythagorean Triples, and Borders Differences, **Zenodo**, June 14, 2019, pp. 1-59, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3246586>.

[16] **Inder J. Taneja**, Symmetric Properties of Nested Magic Squares, **Zenodo**, June 29, 2019, pp. 1-55, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3262170>.

[17] **Inder J. Taneja**, General Sum Symmetric and Positive Entries Nested Magic Squares, **Zenodo**, July 04, 2019, pp. 1-55, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3268877>.

[18] **Inder J. Taneja**, Bordered Magic Squares With Order Square Magic Sums, **Zenodo**, January 20, 2020, pp. 1-26, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3613690>.

[19] **Inder J. Taneja**, Fractional and Decimal Type Bordered Magic Squares With Magic Sum 2020. **Zenodo**, January 20, 2020, pp.1-25. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3613698>.

[20] **Inder J. Taneja**, Fractional and Decimal Type Bordered Magic Squares With Magic Sum 2021, **Zenodo**, December 16, 2020, pp. 1-33, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4327333>.

[21] **Inder J. Taneja**, Inder J. Taneja, Block-Wise and Block-Bordered Magic Squares With Magic Sum 2022, **Zenodo**, December 28, 2021, pp. 1-38, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5807789>

• Block-Bordered Magic Squares

[22] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Prime and Double Prime Numbers - I, **Zenodo**, August 18, 2020, pp. 1-81, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3990291>.

[23] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Prime and Double Prime Numbers - II, **Zenodo**, August 18, 2020, pp. 1-90, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3990293>.

[24] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Prime and Double Prime Numbers - III, **Zenodo**, September 01, 2020, pp. 1-93, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4011213>.

• Double-Digit Bordered Magic Squares

[25] **Inder J. Taneja**, Two Digits Bordered Magic Squares Multiples of 4: Orders 8 to 24, **Zenodo**, April, 26, 2023, pp. 1-43, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7866956>.

[26] **Inder J. Taneja**, Two Digits Bordered Magic Squares of Orders 28 and 32, **Zenodo**, April, 26, 2023, pp. 1-36, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7866981>.

[27] **Inder J. Taneja**, Two Digits Bordered Magic Squares of Orders 10, 14, 18 and 22, **Zenodo**, April, 30, 2023, pp. 1-43, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7880931>.

[28] **Inder J. Taneja**, Two Digits Bordered Magic Squares of Orders 26 and 30, **Zenodo**, April, 30, 2023, pp. 1-45, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7880937>.

[29] **Inder J. Taneja**, Two Digits Bordered Magic Squares of Orders 36 and 40, **Zenodo**, May, 04, 2023, pp. 1-41, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7896709>.

[30] **Inder J. Taneja**, Two digits Bordered Magic Squares of Orders 34 and 38, **Zenodo**, May 10, 2023, pp. 1-45, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7922571>.

[31] **Inder J. Taneja**, New Concepts in Magic Squares: Double Digits Bordered Magic Squares of Orders 7 to 108, **Zenodo**, August 09, 2023, pp. 1-30, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8230214>.

• Cornered Magic Squares

[32] **Inder J. Taneja**, Cornered Magic Squares of Order 6, **Zenodo**, May 23, 2023, pp. 1-23, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7960679>.

- [33] **Inder J. Taneja**, Cornered Magic Squares of Orders 5 to 13, **Zenodo**, June 03, 2023, pp. 1-71, <https://10.5281/zenodo.8000467>.
- [34] **Inder J. Taneja**, Cornered Magic Squares of Orders 14 to 24, **Zenodo**, June 03, 2023, pp. 1-39, <https://10.5281/zenodo.8000471>.
- [35] **Inder J. Taneja**, New Concepts in Magic Squares: Cornered Magic Squares of Orders 5 to 81, **Zenodo**, August 09, 2023, pp. 1-27, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8231157>.
- [36] **Inder J. Taneja**, Cornered Magic Squares in Construction of Magic Squares of Orders 16, 20, 24 and 28, **Zenodo**, August 23, 2023, <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=10172>.
- [37] **Inder J. Taneja**, Striped and Semi-Striped Cornered Magic Squares of Orders 6 to 50, <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=15048>,
March 17, 2025
- [38] **Inder J. Taneja**, New Concepts in Magic Squares: Cornered Magic Squares of Orders 5 to 108, **Zenodo**, January 29, 2025, pp. 1-33, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14759238>.
-